

**SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL DETERMINANTS OF URBAN CRIME
AMONG YOUTHS IN LAGOS STATE.**

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ABSTRACT

The need for safety has always been one of the most profound needs of human, and how to reduce criminal activities is a major challenge that any government must seek to address through policies and programs. Fulfilling this need and resolving this issue has become more complicated with the increase and complications of societies. The primary goal of this study is to examine social and environmental determinants of urban crime among youths and the findings demonstrates the needs for a participatory approach, which considers all stakeholders and the communities. More precisely, the study sought an understanding of the relationships between place of resident and street violence; influences of peer group; family background; influences of educational attainment; relationship between employment status and thuggery perpetration; and social work approaches towards urban crime among youths. This study involved the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data from respondents in the selected local government areas of Lagos. Quantitative data was collected from youth respondents between the ages of 18-35 with the use of questionnaire, while qualitative data was obtained from police officers in the study area with the aid of Key Informant Interview (KII) Guide. The results of the study found a relationship between place of residence and street fighting among young people which; shows that urban crime is more concentrated in low income areas where there are more unemployed youths; and corroborates with differential association theory that peer influence is correlated with urban crime. It also shows that there is no relationship between family background and urban crime among youths; there is no relationship between educational attainment and urban crime among youths; accessibility in low income areas (ghetto) is higher than middle and upper class areas; and, there is a relationship between employment status and urban crime among youths.

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that, the State should review its current urban planning and also embrace community-based approaches; the current state of youth unemployment in Nigeria, particularly in Lagos metropolis, should be addressed holistically and with a sense of urgency; education curriculum should be reviewed at all levels of education to incorporate skills; and, the formal criminal justice and policing systems should be strengthened as it is important that the police and the criminal justice systems are 'fit for purpose' and are seen as key contributors to the fight against crime.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Concern about urban safety and the involvement of young people in criminal activities never seems to diminish, nor does concern about youth gangs and their contribution to urban crime. They seem always to have been a feature of urban life on every continent. While in different countries and decades there may have been periods of relative calm, anxiety about increasing rates of crime, youth offending and gang membership often recur (Margaret, 2007). Young people are usually identified as the major threat to public order in urban areas and as a major source of insecurity. Criminal activities have become more frightening in the world today and it is a major source of social concern. In Nigeria for instance, all daily newspapers devote a significant proportion of column to reports of murder and theft. The announcement concerning murder, rape, burglary and stolen vehicles among others are daily features on the news and national dailies.

Although crime occurrence has no boarder, but several empirical studies suggest that crime is more concentrated in areas where there are high population densities, swift changes in social environments and poor living conditions which are characteristics of urban settlements (Ghani, 2017; Malik,2016; Kunnuji, 2016). Even within a particular urban society, there are these variations between ‘hotspots and cold spots’ locations. Hotspot locations are those areas where the frequency of crimes is high because of the presence of high crime attractors while on the other hand, cold spot locations are areas with low crime (low crime attractors). This is because of the differences in geographical areas in terms of socio-environmental, economic, political and demographic characteristics. In light of this, crime has become one of the serious social problems and burning issues to all societies because it affects the public safety and quality of life among the people, as it affects all, irrespective of race, religion, gender and income levels.

In Nigeria and many developing countries, industrialization and unplanned urbanization characterized the economic and social growth processes. The spatial expression of these realities and the consequence of simultaneous urbanization with the uncontrolled growth pattern in the most of the urban cities are manifested in diverse urban problems such as crime and violence. The spatial distribution of crime incident varies in accordance with type of settlement area. The most

obvious difference is between urban and rural area with a much wider range of crimes securing in urban environments (Lasisi and Olapeju, 2016). These clearly results from the fact that there are far more goods available in cities to be stolen and sold. However, it also reflects the fact that increasing numbers of people have moved to the cities in recent decades only to find themselves living in slum areas in situation of social exclusion (Cozens, 2006). In many urban centers of Nigeria today, criminals activities and violence have assumed dangerous tendencies as they threaten lives and property, the national sense of well-being and reduces the citizen's quality of life (Agbola, 2004; Ahmed 2010).

The fear of armed robbery, kidnapping, and terrorism, as being experienced in the northern states, make citizens to be perpetually unsafe, displaced, deprived, mentally disturbed, and geographically unstable. With an average of one policeman to 5000 Nigerians as the police strength, compared to one of policeman to 400 persons in the developed world, and the inadequacy of internal security infrastructure, the police force is constrained, vulnerable and sometimes helpless (Lasisi and Olapeju, 2016). Some studies have suggested that urban crime is inevitable response to increasing disparities of income and access to services, housing, education, health and security, in addition to long-term poverty and unemployment. Furthermore, children and young people now represent up to 50 per cent of the population of many cities and megacities, especially in less developed countries, and constitute up to half of the urban poor (Margaret, 2007; Smith and Bradshaw, 2005).

A critical look at the problem of criminal activities in urban areas shows that there is socio-environmental and demographic dimension to urban crime in Nigerian cities and elsewhere in the world. In recent years, rapid urbanization and deteriorating social and economic urban conditions combined with increasing proportions of children and young people, especially among the urban poor, have all contributed to providing fertile ground for the recruitment of young people into groups and gangs engaged in local crime and violence. The growth of transnational organized crime, most obviously manifest in the trafficking in small arms, drugs and persons, has facilitated that recruitment and exacerbated the associated violence (World Health Organization, 2002). Lasisi and Olapeju (2016) observed that the majority of perpetrators and victims of urban violence are young men who are between 15 and 25 years old, an age when both men and women are at greatest risk of exploitation, crime and victimization.. Lasisi and Olapeju, (2016) observed further that the majority of perpetrators and victims of urban violence are young men who are between 15

to 25 years old, an age when both men and women are at greatest risk of exploitation crime and victimization.

In the last two decades, the nature and frequencies of urban crimes in many parts of the world have increased precipitously as it has been observed that the entire world is experiencing high crime rate (Usman, Yakubu and Bello 2012). The high level of urban crime activities has become more alarming and contributed to decline in the socio-economic development and quality of life (Badiora & Afon, 2013; Marzbali, Abdullah, Abd Razak, and Tilaki, M. 2011). This is connected to the opportunities offered by ‘crime attractors’ in such areas which turn them to be seen as ‘hotspots’. Tabangin, Flores, & Emperador (2008) opined that these opportunities are related to the location, movement patterns of offenders and potential targets.

Crime is generally influenced by the criminal behaviour of offenders, the existence of attractive targets in an area and absence of capable security agencies. Therefore, in any circumstances for a crime to be committed, there must be a motivated offender, a suitable target (attractor) and the absence of a capable security force. In reality these ‘criminal behaviours’ and potentialities for criminal activities in places are inherent in human society. Usman, Yakubu and Bello (2012) asserted that crime is an ‘inescapable reality in human life, therefore, no national characteristics, no political regime, and no system of law, police or judiciary have rendered a country free from crime.

There is no singular factor that can be the cause of crimes or criminal behaviour because of the divergent and complexity of human behaviours. Different types of crimes are being committed by different types of people, at different times, in different places and under different circumstances (Dambazau, 2007). However, many researchers opined that unemployment and poverty are the root causes of criminal behaviours (Katsina, 2013; Song et al., 2013; Kien, 2015; Sewuese, 2014). In conformity with this, Ajaegbu (2012) in a study in Nigeria reported, the problem of crimes in Nigeria has been exacerbated by the high rate of ‘unemployment and economic hardship which has pushed many jobless youths, some of whom are graduates, into various deadly crimes’. While in a contrasting argument, Soh (2012) explained that criminal behaviour can be found in all types of people; even people who wallow in wealth can commit crimes.

Social work as a profession and an academic discipline is concerned with urban population safety and youth welfare. Social workers can enhance their knowledge of the issues facing a particular group of youth by examining empirical evidence specific to that group. Society tends to focus on negative behavioral outcomes rather than the positive attributes that can be enhanced to help youth overcome barriers. Social workers should seek an understanding of disadvantaged groups beyond the models provided by society. At the beginning of the twenty-first century, the aim of social work research, according to Saleebey (2002), is to contribute to the development and evaluation of social work practice and services, to enhance social work's moral purpose, and finally to promote social work inquiry marked by rigour, range, variety, depth and progression.

Therefore, this study will examine the relationship between social and environmental factors such as place of residence, family background, peer group, educational attainment, employment status, and their implications for and relationship with urban crime such as street fight, armed robbery, vandalization, drug peddling and rape. The study will also examine the roles of social workers in ameliorating urban crime among youths.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The growth in urban crime rate in Nigeria is one of the major social problems facing the country in recent time. The dominance of crime in developing countries increases the volatility of the issue. The concentration of crimes in major urban centers worldwide is therefore heralded as an indicator of the breakdown of urban systems. Nigeria urban cities like Lagos are experiencing breakdown of law and increased criminal activities that threaten lives and properties as well as peace of law abiding citizens (Agboola, 2000; Ahmed, 2010). This has led to the formation of various vigilante groups, to combat crimes in some parts of the country (Fajemirokun et al., 2006).

Urbanization, as considered from the economic point of view is good as it facilitates achievement of economies and thus promotes growth of industries and development in the economy. However, taking the social point of view urbanization encourages crimes as is evident from the fact that the rate of crime is higher in large cities and in urbanized areas as has been proved by many empirical studies. Urbanization per se is not the only cause for rising trend of crime, but, there are many other determinants alongside urbanization and closely related to it, that have a direct say in the

rising trend of crimes in urbanized areas. These are unemployment, inflation, income inequality, dysfunctional family and lack of quality education especially for the youths.

Public safety is increasingly determined by crime and security in urban spaces. The marginalization and exclusion of youth living in poverty has coincided with the breakdown of traditional family structures or social and cultural networks; the impact of HIV/AIDS; increased crime and violence in urban areas, including organized crime; increased trafficking in drugs and small arms; sexual exploitation and trafficking in persons; youth crime and victimization; and increased fear and insecurity (Margaret, 2007). City and national governments are increasingly under pressure to respond to crime with tough and repressive measures.

How the public safety problem in urban spaces is dealt with in the 21st century as urbanization intensifies will determine citizens' perceptions of the accountability and effectiveness of the state in upholding the social contract between the citizens and the state. In many of the world's major cities, law enforcement and social development have not caught up with the pace of urbanization, and there is a deep and growing bifurcation between developed and reasonably safe sectors of economic growth and social advancement and slums stuck in a trap of poverty, marginalization, and violence. Addressing the violence and lifting the slums from this trap will be among the major challenges for many governments.

Social workers in their quest to intervene and reduce urban crime among youths and bring about improved living condition encounter challenges that are rooted in social structure. Therefore, social work practitioners recognize the fact that structural exclusion happens everywhere, and the need for personal support to cope with social problems is an individual need, and the empowerment of people or groups is necessary all over the country. Unfortunately, the roles of social workers has not been recognized in Nigeria and many developing countries as the country become more urbanized and as the crime statistics indicate that there is a need for professional approach towards urban crime and its overall effects on the quality of life of citizen. To this extent the study seeks an understanding of the social-environmental determinants of urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos, and social work approach towards urban crime among youths will also be investigated.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The general objective of the study is to examine the influence of social and environmental factors on urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos. In addition to that, this study also has the following specific objectives:

1. To investigate the relationship between place of residence and urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State.
2. To examine the influence of peer group on urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State.
3. To understand the relationship between family background and urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State.
4. To explore the relationship between educational attainment and urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State.
5. To investigate the relationship between employment status and urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research study seeks to provide answers to the following research questions through analysis of data that will be collected from the field of study:

1. What is the relationship between place of residence and urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State?
2. What is the influence of peer group on urban crime involvement among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State?
3. What is the relationship between family background and urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State?
4. What is the influence of educational attainment on urban crime involvement among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State?
5. What is the relationship between employment status and urban crime among youths in selected local government areas of Lagos State?

1.5 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

1. **H₁**: There is a relationship between place of residence and urban crime
H₀: There is no relationship between place of residence and urban crime
2. **H₁**: There is a relationship between Peer group influence and urban crime
H₀: There is no relationship between Peer group influence and urban crime
3. **H₁**: There is a relationship between family background and urban crime
H₀: There is no relationship between family background and urban crime
4. **H₁**: There is a relationship between educational attainment and urban crime
H₀: There is no relationship between educational attainment and urban crime
5. **H₁**: There is a relationship between employment status and urban crime
H₀: There is a relationship between employment status and urban crime

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The need for safety has always been one of the most profound needs of human, and how to reduce criminal activities is a major challenge that any government must seek to address through policies and programs. Fulfilling this need and resolving this issue has become more complicated with the increase and complication of societies. Over the year, governments across the world have spent billions of dollars generated from tax payers' revenue to combat crime, especially crime in urban modern cities. Despite spending this huge amount of money, criminal activities continue to be part of law abiding citizens' daily experience. Most of these efforts have been focused on equipping security agencies with sophisticated weapons and intelligence units that are proactive in detecting and combating crime. Hence, the needs arise to emphasis muti-sectoral approach that considers the importance of certain key social indicators and involvement of several stakeholders in the war against crime. The findings of this study will demonstrate the needs for a participatory approach, which considers all stakeholders and professional such as social workers, government, the security personnel and the communities.

The study and its findings will also contribute significantly to the existing literature on the relationship between socio-environmental factors and urban crime among youths. Furthermore, the findings of this study will generate empirical facts that can lead to development of evidence-based interventions that are capable of improving youth welfare and empower them to contribute

significantly to social development. The study will be of significant benefit to policymakers as well as government and non-government agencies in their efforts to formulate effective policies and program to eradicate crime to its barest minimum.

1.6 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study seeks an understanding of social and environmental determinants of urban crime in selected local government areas of Lagos. Indices of urban crime will be matched against some social and environmental indices for regression analysis. More precisely, the study seeks an understanding of the relationships between place of resident and street violent; influences of peer group on vandalization of government utility installations; family background and stealing; influences of educational attainment on illicit drug use; relationship between employment status and thuggery perpetration; and social work approaches towards urban crime among youths. The study will involve collection of both quantitative and qualitative data from respondents in the selected local government areas of Lagos. Quantitative data will be collected from youth respondents, who are between the ages of 18-35, with the use of questionnaire, while qualitative data will be obtained from police officers in the study area with the aid of Key Informant Interview (KII) Guide. Extensive review of literature will also be done to have an understanding of social work approach towards. Hence, both quantitative and qualitative methods of data analysis will be involved.

The study will likely pose some limitations in the areas of finance to conduct the research, availability and willingness of the respondents to participate in the study and sparse literature to support the research study. However, the researcher is determined to ensure that these limitations are taken into consideration and find best possible means to ensure that the research inquiry is successful.

1.7 CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

The following concepts are defined as they are used within the context of this study:

1. Crime

There is no universal definition of crime. This is as a result of changes in social, political, psychological and economic conditions. An act may be a crime in one society, but not in another (Danbazau, 2007). For example, prostitution, adultery and homosexuality between consenting adults have been wholly or partially removed from the criminal law in USA but are considered as crimes in Sub-Sahara Africa countries and Muslim communities such as Saudi Arabia. However, for the purpose of this study the definition of crime according to Scott & Marshall, 2005 (As cited in Kunnuji, 2016) as “the breaking of prohibitory laws, to which legitimate punishments are attached as the breaking of prohibitory laws, to which legitimate punishments are attached” for the protection of the public.

2. Crime rate

This refers to the frequency at which crime occur in a particular location, which is likely to be different from another location. The high variance of crime rates across time and space is one of the oldest puzzles in the social sciences. Crime rate is normally expressed as the number of crimes per 100,000. In order to calculate this, the formula would look like this:

$$\frac{\text{Number of Crimes}}{\text{Population}} \times 100,000 = \text{Crime Rate Per 100,000}$$

3. Urban area

An urban area is a human settlement with high population density and infrastructure of built environment. Urban areas are created through urbanization and are categorized by urban morphology as cities, towns, conurbations or suburbs. In urbanism, the term contrasts to rural areas such as villages and hamlets and in urban sociology or urban anthropology it contrasts with natural environment. The creation of early predecessors of urban areas during the urban revolution led to the creation of human civilization with modern urban planning, which along with

other human activities such as exploitation of natural resources leads to human impact on the environment.

4. Urban crime

The concept of urban crime describes the notion that certain types of criminal activities are more noticeable, frequent, and are attributes of densely populated areas of urban settlement as opposed to rural.

5. Violence

The definition of violence according to WHO (2002) is adopted in this study. Hence, violence is “the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community, which either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, maldevelopment, or deprivation”.

6. Youth

The Nigerian National Youth Policy (2009) definition of youth is adopted for this study. Therefore, a youth is defined here as any person between the ages of 18-35 years old.

7. Social Work

Social work is a helping profession and an academic discipline that is concerned with individuals, families, groups and communities with the aim of enhancing their individual and collective well-being. It aims to help people develop their skills and their ability to use their own resources and those of the community to resolve problems. Social work is concerned with individual and personal problems but also with broader social issues such as poverty, unemployment and domestic violence. Human rights and social justice are the philosophical underpinnings of social work practice. The uniqueness of social work practice is in the blend of some particular values, knowledge and skills, including the use of relationship as the basis of all interventions and respect for the client’s choice and involvement.

8. Social work approach

This refers to the methods, theories, models as well as the intervention techniques adopted by social work practitioners in responding to solve any social problem presented before them or encountered during the course of their service delivery. It encompasses a range of different intervention strategies and methods utilized by social workers to render professional service to those in need of it (clients) and solve their individual, group/family and community problems. A key element of the social work process is the selection of intervention methods, informed by psychological and sociological theories, and social work assessments. Through skills of observation and assessment, social workers are able to analyse and explain situations, develop hypotheses about potential outcomes, and select intervention methods to achieve desired outcomes.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The research literature on urban crime is generally of two types. There are studies that compare cities, seeking to understand why some have higher crime rates than others. And there are studies that focus on explaining variations in crime levels within cities. However, both types of studies use similar theories and focus on the same social forces to understand their observations. The focus of this present study is on the second approach because the study seeks to understand social and environmental determinants of crime within Lagos metropolis, which of one of the most urbanized cities in Africa. More precisely, this chapter examines the concept crime; urbanization process and crime, youths and urban crime, and socio-environmental context of urban crime. The chapter also involves review on the themes of the study objectives including the relationship between place of resident and street violent among youths; influences of peer group on vandalization of government utility installations among youths; family background and stealing among youths; education attainment and illicit drug use among youths; employment status and thuggery among youths.

2.2 The Concept of Crime

The concept of crime like other concepts in social sciences, which have no generally accepted definition. According to Scott and Marshall (2009), “a crime is held to be an offence, which goes beyond the personal and into the public sphere, breaking prohibitory rules or laws, to which legitimate punishments or sanctions are attached, and which requires the intervention of a public authority. For crime to be known as such, it must come to the notice of, and be processed through, an administrative system or enforcement agency. It must be reported and recorded by the police (or other investigator); it may then become part of criminal statistics; may or may not be investigated; and may or may not result in a court case.”

Dambazau (2007) defined crime as an act or omission against public interest and which is prescribed by law enacted by the legislature in the overall interests of the society, and to which prescribed punishment is attached in the event of violation and it involves four major principles which are public wrong, moral wrong, law and punishment for the criminal. Crime is also seen as

a violation of the rules agreed to be respected by all members of the society, and upon which the rest members of the society mete sanction upon those guilty of the violation. It is for the same reason that the legal system views crime as a public and moral wrong. The prevalence of crime in the world today is a cause for serious concern for all and sundry. It undermines the social fabric by eroding the sense of safety and security. Crime impacts on society in a variety of ways according to the nature and extent of crime committed. It constitutes a problem when its incidence is as rampant in the society as to constitute a threat to the security of persons and property, as well as social order and solidarity (Onoge, 1998).

Crime is a threat to the economic, political and social security of a nation and a major factor associated with underdevelopment; because it discourages both local and foreign investments, reduces the quality of life, destroys human and social capital, damages relationship between citizens and the states, thus undermining democracy, rule of law and the ability of the country to promote development. The development in societies with particular references to westernization has not helped matters; instead, it has been destructive to the social and cultural values of the society (Adebayo, 2013).

Reasons for the increase in crime in Nigeria include urbanization which is spreading more widely and rapidly than improvement in the social and economic condition. Crime is a huge threat to public safety. It causes great personal suffering, vast material damage, and place enormous burden on the urban social network. Globally, every five years, 60% of city inhabitants have been victims of one type of crime or another while over half of these crimes have involved personal crime (arson, fraudulence, cheating, 419 syndrome, forgery, etc). It has been noted that Nigerian cities are conducive areas for criminal activities because they provide the anonymity needed for criminal activities (Okafor, 2011).

2.3 Urbanization Process and Crime among Youths

Rapid shift of the population from rural areas to urban centres, a process referred to as urbanization, is occurring in both developed and developing countries; however, space of urbanization is faster in developing world, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa and Asian sub-regions, where people from neglected rural areas migrate to the urban areas expecting employment and better living conditions (Obeng-Odoom, 2013; Oteng-Ababio and Melara, 2014; Agyei-Mensah et al., 2015; Ghani, 2017).

However, many immigrants with expectation of improved quality of life would soon realize that urbanization itself does not offer “green pasture”, rather urbanization offers its own peculiar opportunities and challenges that only the fittest can survive (Behrens and Robert-Nicoud, 2010).

According to the statistics from United Nations, the world population expected to reach 8.3 billion and 9.1 billion in 2030 and 2050 respectively, 4.9 billion of this population is expected to settle down in urban areas in 2030 and 6.3 billion in 2050. In 2010 alone, about 3.5 billion from 6.9 billion or 71% of the world population live in urban areas with Asia (1.7 billion), Europe (0.5 billion), Latin America and Caribbean (0.4 billion), Africa (0.4 billion), Northern America (0.3 billion) and Oceania (0.02 billion) (United Nation, 2007). This lead to unprecedented trends: the urban dwellers increased from only 220 million in 1900 to 736 million in 1950 and now reached 3.5 billion in 2010 (United Nation, 2007).

Knight and Gunatilaka (2007) stated that a migrant takes into account the probability of obtaining a desired urban employment at any time. In another study, Soh (2012) also argued that it is in urban areas where all the facilities are well built to make human life more comfortable, and the main attraction of urban is easy access to wealth. Harris and Todaro, 1970 (as cited in Ghani, 2017) described it as “proceeds in response to urban-rural differences in expected earning”. Although, in certain cases, many urban immigrants assumed they will secure employment, when usually it is not the case. Instead, they meet a cost of living that is much higher or rather difficult than that of their experience back in rural areas. Hence, the rapid pace of urbanization in developing regions like Africa is occurring within the context of macroeconomic stability and growth across many countries in the regions (Grant, 2015). Commenting further on Africa’s macroeconomic growth in recent decades, Grant notes that a ‘narrow elite is benefiting disproportionately and the poor and unemployed are being left behind.

Current growth is neither inclusive nor democratic: unregulated, informal economic activities are very common in urban Africa, both in terms of the numbers of informally employed and in terms of the goods and services provided by the informal economy’. It is within the context of economic growth and urbanization that urban crime is noted to be on the rise largely due to weak governance systems and limited infrastructure and services, including policing (Abrahamsen and Williams, 2005). Urbanization has created numerous social problems, among which is crime that became a common phenomenon to all urban areas in both developed and developing nations. Recent

unimaginable levels of the world urbanization coincides with rise in urban crimes in many parts of the world, as the rate of unemployment had been on the increase and coupled with increased poverty among the urban poor.

According to Ghani (2017), impulsive crime takes place in areas where there are high population densities, swift changes in social environments and poor living conditions, which are the characteristic of many urban areas, especially in Africa. For instance, many immigrants in urban areas experience new urban life where relationship is based on momentary, superficial and impersonal interactions. This then produce anonymity among urban dwellers, diabolical socio-economic, high cost of living and socially disorganized neighborhoods, thereby turning some to steal, rob, become drunkards, drug pushers and prostitutes to make ends meet. This idea is supported by Soh (2012), who states that “secondary relations eventually lead to family breakup, alcoholism, crime, and other negative aspects of urban life”. Although he further clarified that, ‘urban life does not automatically lead to social disorganization, but it does increase the opportunities to be exposed to deviance and negative effects on one's behaviour as there are many promoters of such acts, or else when the condition warrants it. Therefore some other factors cause urban crimes in all its ramifications other than urbanization.

Ultimately rapid growth in urbanization had a direct relationship with the increase in crime as the rate of unemployment had been on the increase, high cost of living coupled with housing problem (homelessness) and these in turn lead to all sorts of urban problems crime inclusive (Okafor, 2011; Ajaegbu, 2012; Soh, 2012; Usman, Yakubu and Bello, 2012). Urban areas are highly heterogeneous in all its socio-cultural and economic ramifications where various good and deviances can be found. Soh (2012) opines that all ‘forms of deviance flourish within urban environments because there are more individuals who support this subculture’. These sub-cultures led to committing various crimes in urban areas and continuous increase in crime in such areas are correlated with the rapid development in urbanism.

According to Katsina (2013a), crippled economy, high levels of urban poverty, unemployment and inequality are the causal factors of urban crimes. This is to say that there is a closely interwoven linkage between economic situations in any given society or a country with unemployment and crimes. Likewise Ajaegbu (2012) opined that unemployment and economic hardship have pushed many ‘jobless youths, some of whom are graduates, into various deadly crimes. Katsina (2013)

found unemployment is the main causes for ‘eruption and escalation of crimes in urban areas across the breadth of Nigeria’. Soh (2012) posits ‘unemployment is closely linked to crime’ no matter the region of the World. He also argued that urban crimes are influenced

Urban areas are regarded as centres of opportunities that have become engines for economic growth, centres of diversity and changes. In urban areas the residents live, work and interact within their confined physical environment, matching up with criminal prospects rendered themselves within these same confined environments which instilled fear into the minds of many. In recent decades crime has become a universal phenomenon in its varying forms in all cultures. Prevalent of crime in urban areas make it seen as a space of geographical fear for many and the fear is not restricted to one's age, class, gender or race. Urban stability and sustainability has been connected to safety of securing and policing of urban areas. Issues of personal safety and security became linked with urban ‘live ability’ and ‘quality of life’ and addressing crime has become a significant benchmark for a city's quality of life (England and Simon, 2010; Tretter, 2013; Ahmed and Salihu, 2013).

Although some analysts (e.g. Potts, 2012) have questioned the mantra of rapid urbanization in Sub-Saharan Africa, a critical analysis of the continent’s demographic trends suggests an urban future rather than persistence of its present largely rural character (Grant, 2015). However, as earlier noted, Africa’s present urbanization process is severely challenged. At the heart of the challenges is the weak governance and planning of the continent’s cities. According to Berrisford (2013), planning is very critical for inclusive and sustainable urban development as it offers opportunity to ‘regulate land use and land development, provide a sound basis for infrastructure planning, secure the rights of investors [and citizens], protect environmental resources and mitigate environmental risks’.

However, as Watson and Agbola (2013) sadly note, Africa’s cities (such Lagos) are growing and changing rapidly, but lack appropriate planning, leading to an increasingly chaotic, inefficient and unsustainable urban development. A widely shared view in the criminology and sociology literature is that unplanned neighbourhoods and cities with their socio-economic manifestations of poverty and deprivation can facilitate crime and the fear of crime (Lersch, 2007; Brunton-Smith and Jackson, 2012; Landman, 2012). In the context of limited public police services, households and neighbourhoods in urban areas feeling insecure have responded by target hardening their

homes (use of metal burglary proofs) resulting in negative consequences, particularly weakened community bonding and social cohesion.

In other instances, households and neighbourhoods have resorted to extra-judicial and instant justice measures such as lynching of crime suspects or the use of the youth as discussed in Oteng-Ababio (2016). Other measures including the employment of the services of “vigilante” and private security guards especially in wealthy households and neighbourhoods, with cost implications for these households (Owusu, Oteng-Ababio, Owusu and Wrigley-Asante, 2016). According to UN-Habitat (2007), traditional or conventional approach of crime and violence as the primary responsibility of the police and the criminal justice system is increasingly being replaced by an approach that recognizes that the complexity of the phenomenon being addressed requires a broad-based response’. Notwithstanding this fact, there is still the need to strengthen the police service and the judiciary system as they remain very critical in the fight against urban crime.

2.3 Youths Involvement in Urban Crime

Youth involvement in urban criminal activities has been an issue of concern for government, law enforcement agencies, the general public and other stakeholders. Youths are perceived to be the major perpetrators of crime in urban areas, and they are seen as threat to social order (Margaret, 2007). Studies of young offenders show that young people generally commit minor offences and most are likely to ‘grow out of crime (Tretter, 2013). However, the Federation of Community Legal Centres (2012) contends that this perception of young people is heavily shaped by the media, and that reports of a wave of youth crime are generally selective in their presentation of the facts relating to youth offending.

While there is contention about the extent to which youths are involved in crime, there seems to be a general consensus among social researchers that young people are different to adults in that they are more susceptible to certain risk factors, which may push them to join criminal gang especially in urban area, due to their stage of mental and emotional development (Lersch, 2007). According to Witte (1996), family disruption, drug and alcohol abuse, limited economic opportunities and unemployment, unoccupied and unsupervised youths are all found to be associated with urban crime. Young people are at greater risk of mental health problems, alcohol and drug abuse which may which may trigger violence and criminal behavior. Concerns about

youth crime also revolves around factors such access to small arms and links with more organized adult gangs.

The economics of crime are mostly related with factors such as poverty, income inequality, social exclusion, cultural characteristics, age, sex, education level and family background (Buonanno, 2003). Various observations indicate that most of the youth are in crime because of poverty, which drove them into criminal acts for survival (Prior and Paris, 2005). A study conducted at revealed that over 70%; more than 40 out of 55 of the inmates were poor or came from poor family backgrounds based on where they lived, property ownership and the types of offences committed. For instance, some boys indicate that they had run from home to beg for survival in the streets because they lacked basic needs. In those streets they latter committed crimes to survive, they were involved in petty offences like stealing goods or properties.

Closely related to issue of poverty among youths is unemployment. Unemployment rate among youths in developing countries, particularly Africa, has continued to be on the increase despite the abundant natural resources available in the region. In Tanzania, for example, the rate of unemployment remained high which was estimated at 11.7% in 2006 for persons aged from 15 years and above (National Employment Policy, 2008). Chronic youth's unemployment is evident in Nigeria. Every year, thousands of graduates are produced but there are no jobs for majority of them. Nigerian streets are littered with youth hawkers who ordinarily would have found gainful employment in some enterprise (Okafor, 2011). The large number of youths who are unemployed is capable of undermining democratic practice as they constitute a serious threat if engaged by the political class for clandestine and criminal activities (Adepegba, 2011; Okafor, 2011).

The relationship between crime and unemployment has been ambiguous in most studies, leading to different approaches. The first one indicates a positive relationship (Raphael and Ebmer, 2001; Edmark, 2005), known as "motivation effect", where a rise in unemployment rates leads to economic problems and increases the motivation to engage in criminal acts. The second one comes from the work of Cantor and Land (1985), who found a negative correlation known as "opportunity effect" (Melick, 2004) and indicates that, during economic depression a rise in unemployment rates leads to decrease in median family income and discourages a person from the decision to commit a crime.

In addition to menace of unemployment among youths in urban cities, drug and alcohol is another risk factor for crime perpetration among young people. In urban areas, it often appears that drugs and crime among young people, particularly violent crime, are inextricably linked. According to Witte (1996), drugs are typically expensive and often reduce young people's eligibility and motivation to hold a job. The combination results in an increased proclivity to commit crimes, which may turn violent. Because drugs are traded in an underground economy in distressed neighbourhoods, those who feel cheated in transaction have no legal recourse and must take matters into their own hands, often through violence. Turfs wars break out between drug providers operating in a regulatory and legal vacuum, so the distribution of even relatively benign drugs such as marijuana may precipitate violence. The underground economy in ghetto areas, with its tenuous ties to legal institutions and its need for secrecy, provides a congenial environment for criminal activities among young people.

In Central America and the Caribbean, the deportation of gang members from the United States has been seen as a major factor in the recent increase in gang-formation and organized violence in that region (Dowdney, 2005). The 2006 Small Arms Survey of the Graduate Institute of International Studies in Geneva, Switzerland, has analyzed the devastating impact that the traffic in small arms has had in terms of increasing the level of lethal violence among young men in countries in various regions, from sub-Saharan Africa to Latin America, from the Caribbean to Polynesia (Bevan and Florquin, 2006).

In many countries, therefore, Governments are being pressured to act against real or perceived increases in youth gang activity and violence, and to use tougher laws and sentences. In the United States, a century of research into youth gangs has gathered ample evidence not only of their existence, but also of their specific characteristics. In other developed countries, youth gangs are a more recent concern. A combination of general worries about crime, media attention and specific events has led many countries to investigate their own experience and to look for evidence of youth gang problems.

In England and Wales, the first official survey of delinquent youth groups was only conducted in 2004 and a study of the links between youth groups, gangs and weapons was published in 2007 (Sharp, Aldridge and Medina, 2006; Youth Justice Board, 2007). In Scotland, the first specific study was conducted in 2001 (Smith and Bradshaw, 2005). Both England and Scotland, among

others, are reluctant to label youth groups as “gangs” because of the dangers of creating or reinforcing gang identities. The Eurogang Project, in place since 1998, has examined youth gang experiences across European countries, often in comparison with the situation in the United States (Klein, Kerner, Maxson, and Weitekamp, 2001).

In most European countries, there is little evidence of the existence of widespread, serious youth gangs modelled on the highly organized, stereotypical youth gang of the United States. Nevertheless, using the definition developed by the Eurogang programme that “a street gang is any durable, street-oriented youth group whose involvement in illegal activity is part of their group identity”, surveys of youth in the United States and the Netherlands have found that 8 per cent of the United States sample and 6 per cent of the Dutch sample could be classified as belonging to gangs or “troublesome youth groups” (Esbensen and Weerman, 2005).

In Canada, youth gangs have mainly been the subject of local city studies, in particular in cities such as Winnipeg, Montreal and Toronto (Chatterjee, 2006; Chamandy, 2006). The only national data that exists is a national survey based on police estimates of gang presence conducted in 2002 (Astwood Strategy Corporation, 2003). Until recently, Australia had no national information on the extent or characteristics of youth gangs, although the phenomenon is perceived as an emerging problem. The Ozgang Research Network, inspired by the European example, was established in 2001 (White, 2004).

2.4 Social and Environmental Context of Urban Crime

Although there is general consensus among criminologists and sociologists that urban areas have higher rates of crime than rural areas (Owusu, 2016; Shaw and McKay, 1942; Grants, 2015), of less certainty is why certain urban settings have higher crime rates than other urban settings. That is, not all cities or neighborhoods experience similar levels of crime and violence; there is widespread variation in crime levels across urban spaces. According to Ghani (2017), the nature of urban crime is not uniform but varies from one geographical region to another. In some urban areas, property crime is more common while in others, crime on person (violent) is prevalent. Thus, the question of interest for Criminologists and Sociologists is what is the source of this variation? What causes certain cities or neighborhoods to experience high levels of crime while other cities or neighborhoods enjoy relatively low levels of crime?

The study of crime on an intra-region or intra-urban level began with Henry Shaw's, and later, Clifford McKay's studies of Chicago. During the early-to-mid twentieth century, the research undertaken by Shaw and his associates became the best known of this genre (Shaw and McKay, 1942). Their work in Chicago, rooted in the human ecology model was motivated by the belief that human behavior was best viewed as being situated. Among other things, this meant that the geographic context of human behavior was very important in sociological studies (Shaw, 1929). The last two decades in criminology have seen a strengthening of the sub-discipline of environmental criminology. The focus expanded from the earliest studies in this tradition and now considers a range of aspects of a criminal event.

Crime is not being plagued by a singular factor anywhere it occurred, there are variant factors that influence criminal activities. Notwithstanding, there is a widely-held consensus in crime studies that crime and fear of crime are not equally distributed across cities, and that areas of higher poverty are likely to be areas of high crime incidence as well. This conclusion rests on the view that poor areas of cities characterized by high unemployment rates, family breakdowns, delinquencies and general social disruptions tend to produce alienation and consequently criminal behaviour (Sampson as cited in Cullen, Wright and Blevins, 2016).

While the prevailing conditions of poor areas may produce criminal behavioural tendencies, some analysts have argued that these tendencies can only manifest in the absence of law enforcement agencies such as the police (Fafchamps and Minten, 2005) or guardians as postulated in Cohen and Felson's (1979) routine activity theory. In addition, some experts have pointed to social controls (including strong social cohesion) as having a depressing effect on crime incidence (Plumer, 2010), a point well emphasized in this special issue (Bagson and Owusu, 2016; Frimpong, 2016; Oteng-Ababio, 2016; Owusu, Oteng-Ababio, Owusu and Wrigley-Asante, 2016).

Overall assessment of the literature suggests a correlation between socioeconomic conditions and crime. However, as Pare and Felson (2014) note the interpretation of the relationship remain unclear and the relationship could be spurious as individual and group characteristics can affect both economic success and criminal behaviour, and criminal behaviour in turn can affect individual and group socio-economic conditions as well. Despite this apparent complex relationship between crime and poverty, Pare and Felson (2014) argue that 'most scholars assume that living in poverty increases the likelihood of criminal behaviour'. Attempts to explain the

relationship between crime and economic conditions have remained the heart of crime research and criminological inquiry.

Consequently, many crime theories have explored the extent to which individual and group characteristics as well as the environment influence crime. To explain the possible association between poverty and crime, Pare and Felson (2014) provide three sets of theoretical explanations:

- discrimination and the lack of legitimate opportunities which limits poor people's access to legitimate societal resources and widely shared goals. This situation therefore forces people in poor neighborhoods to access these resources and goals using illegitimate means, and thereby committing crime;
- lower social controls, particularly those associated with disadvantaged neighborhoods, with lower levels of collective efficacy, enhance risks of violence and aggressive behaviours and;
- tendency of people of low socioeconomic status to participate in crime as a results of their socialization experiences leading them to have attitudes that are conducive to crime.

The study of crime committing and the place of crime in 1993 by Brantingham and Brontingham focuses on discovering the interaction between offender and the structural and social environments that are selected as the target of their crime (Kalantari, 2001). Their theory is that crime is the result of interaction between people and movement in the urban perspective of time and place (criminals and victims). Also, there should be four major factors for a crime to be committed: 1) law; 2) offender; 3) target; 4) place (Chung, 2005). In this regard, Bratingham believes that traditional criminology is seeking to find the criminal and his/her incentives in committing a crime. However, crime can be studied without taking personal and individual incentives of a criminal into consideration. Rather, the crime and the environmental conditions of committing it can be focused (Brantingham and Brantingham, 1990).

Environmental criminology includes the study of crime, murder, harm and offence so that the cause of it is first related to special places, and then to the methods that individuals and organizations use forms their activities using spatial place-based factors (Bottoms and Wiles, 1997). Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) includes structural environment design and management in order to minimize the opportunities for committing crime, murder and

offence. Moreover, this notion is based on this assumption that criminals and offenders enter a process of logical decision-making prior to committing a crime. Indeed, the CPTED theories include the methodology of replanting and redesigning the environment based on which architects and urban planners may decrease the chance of fearing crime and offence in order to improve the quality of life (Atlas, 1999).

Generally, CPTED focuses on the grounds where the crime happens and the techniques that will decrease the vulnerability of the environment (Salehi, 2009). This notion is continuously being revised and evaluated and it is established based on four main strategies including territorial integrity, natural supervision, protection of activities and control of accesses (Cozens, 2002). The highly influential theory of “Broken Windows” suggested by Wilson and Kelling focuses on the subject of crime prevention through focusing on the residents’ awareness of suspected behaviors, environmental protection and its consequences (Wilson and Kelling, 1982). According to the Defendable Space theory, the kind of urban design can also help the criminal in selecting crime place as well as committing the crime (Newman, 1973).

Another significant issue to be taken into consideration is the fact that geographic distribution of crimes is influenced by the variables of time and place of committing crime, the criminal and the victim. The studies show that due to their specific structural construction and social, economic and cultural features of residents and users, the potential and opportunity for crime is greater in some places of the city. On the other hand, crime rate is low in some urban areas due to the existence of preventive factors (Kalantari et al, 2009). In fact, crime is not evenly distributed in the city. The idea of crime spots has been increasingly focused during the last few years (Lupton, 1999).

The term “crime spot” was first used by Sherman, Guartain, and Burger in 1969 in order to analyze the offence based on site features. This term refers to a place or geographic area where the offence rate is very high. The limits of this area may include a section of a city, a neighborhood, several neighboring streets or even a residential house or complex. Some have defined “crime spot” as small areas with a high predictable crime rate at least within one year (Kalantari et al., 2009: 80). Some researchers have considered the existence of some occupancies as effective in the formation of crime spots. Sherman, Guartian and Burger have referred to such a relation between the occupancy and the formation of crime spots.

In this regard, Eck, Chainey, Cameron, Leitner and Wilson (2009) have referred to four essential concepts that influence the formation of crime spots:

- A) The presence of the facilities needed for an offence to happen;
- B) Site features such as easy access, unavailability of guards and patrols, lack of appropriate management of sites, and the presence of some facilities encourages the criminals to commit crime in certain places which are typical of disorganized areas in urban cities ;
- C) Crime Targets or the existence of properties and assets that are the offenders' favorites;
- D) The presence of a higher number of offenders and sufficient incentive and ability to commit crime is another effective factor in the formation of crime spots (Eck, Chainey, Cameron, Leitner and Wilson, 2009). Offence Diminishing Center in UK defines crime spots as follows: A geographic area where the frequency of offence is higher than normal (average), or where the occurrence of offence is more frequent compared to the crime distribution in the whole region. According to this definition, a crime spot is a certain area where hosts a high portion of the total crime in the whole area (Kalantari and Tavakoli, 2007) Based on the above-mentioned definition, a crime spot is an area where the mean frequency of offence is more than the surrounding area. This place can be a house, a street corner, a shop or any other place (Sherman, 2014).

2.4.1 Place of Residence and Street Fighting among Youths

Street fighting is a form of street violence involves spontaneous and hostile physical confrontation between two or more individuals where no rules apply. It is a sudden violent encounter that can occur anywhere, in which anything goes (Franco, 2014). Sammy explained further that Street fighting is brutal, unpredictable and extremely dangerous. In many cases, weapons are often used with deadly consequences. He believed that Street fighting can often be avoided by using some form of tactical assessment. Basically, tactical threat assessment is the process of rapidly gathering, analyzing, and accurately evaluating information in terms of threat and danger, including people, places, actions, and objects. There are two broad factors to assess in any street fight, the environment (place of residence) and the assailant. Hence, street fighting often occur in places of residents that have certain characteristics. In Lagos, street fighting usually occur between two rivalry groups or gangs.

Lagos holds many secrets and within its most infamous streets, vices like street fighting, prostitution and drug use sit beside corporate and private wealth. The phenomena of street fights and gangsterism have continued to hold sway in many part of the city. Agbola (1997) noted that in Lagos, an urban city in Nigeria, street fighting, hooliganism and drug dealing were more in high density residential areas. His study demonstrated that there are notable geographical variations in the pattern of street violence and that these variations imply that street fighting is more concentrated in high density neighbourhoods.

Data gathered for the study shows that incidence of street fighting is lowest in the medium density neighbourhoods. This is consistent with the findings of Erodogan (2010) who found crime occurrence to be positively related to density. Mukoro (1994) in contrast, reported high rates of violent crime, including street fighting, in low and medium density areas of Lagos, Nigeria. His interpretation was that areas where people with high socio-economic status resided recorded higher levels of violent crimes. Closer analysis of his presentation, however, showed that this was not consistently so.

Oluogunjobi (2016) clearly demonstrated the fact that street fighting is not equally distributed in Lagos State by identifying 10 areas and streets where crime, including street fighting, occurs regularly. The identified areas include: Anibaba and Itu Nla (Ikorodu); Ojelade and Oju Irin (Mushin); Igbo Olomu and Isawo (Ikorodu); Ilaje (Bariga); Odunfa and Onala (Lagos Island); Shibiri (Okokomaiko); and Obadore (Igando). A close look at this areas shows that they are basically low income neighbourhood with poor basic infrastructure. Some of these areas can also be categorized as high density areas. According to Nigeria 2017 Crime and Safety Report the mainland of Lagos has experienced periodic, violent clashes among localized street gangs known as "Area Boys." The environmental, social health and economic ramifications of this situation in our cities have tremendous impact on urban economy and security (Ogboi 2009). The situation may equally result to increasing residential relocation and decreasing neighbourhood satisfaction. This will adversely affect neighbourhood development.

2.4.2 Influence of Peer Group on Vandalization of Government Utility Installations

Vandalism is an action involving deliberate destruction of public or private property. Within the civic domain, vandalism denotes willful destruction of public or government property in keeping

with criminal or political intent (Uchegbu, Fnes and Achumba, n.d). The word originated from the name of a Germanic tribe, that was well noted for their barbaric way of life during the 4th and 5th century AD, and which sacked Rome in the year 455 AD. A vandal is therefore, a person who has no regard for decency and civilization, and expresses such characteristics by consciously destroying what others have spent time, energy and money to build.

In the context of the present situation in Nigeria, every characteristic feature of the word vandalism has been exhibited in the looting and destruction of public properties in various parts of the country. However, Uchegbu and Achumba, (n.d), noted an additional and alarming feature in this issue is that acts of vandalisation reported in the country in recent years exhibit a touch of sophistication in the mode of operation which indicates proper and conscious organization of the crime. They made reference to breaking of petroleum pipeline in order to steal petroleum products which they noted it requires the use of specialized equipments and resources to break the pipe, collect large commercial quantities of the product, transport it and finally market them.

In a like manner the theft of NEPA transformers and cable cannot be done without the technical skills and other logistic information from NEPA technician themselves, judging from the fact that there is hardly any case of accidental electrocution of the perpetrators during such hazards operations. This according to Uchegbu and Achumba, (n.d) shows that the problem of vandalization of public utilities in the country is not a political issue arising from a spontaneous response to political instability but a clear case of criminal felony. Those that engage in this practice are often criminally minded individuals who want to amass wealth at all cost and at the expense of public welfare (Vidal, 2011).

Peer pressure has been linked to criminal behavior (such as vandalism), but it has not been found to be a primary reason why most people engage in criminal behavior. In the case of adolescents, immaturity has been found to be positively correlated to how much the negative influence of others can impact us to engage in destructive behavior, such as becoming involved in crimes. Kelly (2004) claims that the immaturity found in juveniles around the ages of 16 to 19, can lead to impulsivity and aggressive behavior. This in turn leaves teenagers more vulnerable to peer influence that can lead them to commit crimes.

Hence, vandalism often times represents a collective response that is directed by subcultural values and norms of distinct collectivities such as peer groups within the larger group. Individuals in society will usually make friends or have their closest associates from among their peer groups. Therefore, peer associates have a great influence on the lifestyle of their members. In fact peer group association as an agent of socialization, determines to a large extent, what social codes an individual learns (Allen, 2003; Nsofor, 2013). This implies that individuals whose core group members believe and act criminal within norms will learn and internalize more of criminal codes than those that conform to the norms of the society.

As a result, they conclude that individuals become delinquent through association with people who are the carriers of criminal norms and that criminal behaviour is learned within primary groups in particular, peer groups. That is, vandalization of government utilities among youths is as a result of social influence. It is important to note here, that primary groups are the smallest units of interactions in society and a small group within the society is more likely to have a stronger control over an individual's action or behaviour. In fact, Simmel (1971), observed that "a small group is likely to control the individual completely".

Again, behaviour that is deviant or criminal (such as vandalism) is relative to different social contexts. Societies especially modern ones, consists of various groups with different subcultures. Hence, behaviour that conforms to one particular subculture, maybe considered or viewed deviant outside of it. For example, there might be a strong pressure on a youth to engage in vandalization of government utilities in order to make wealth and make money. So also there may be pressure on someone in a position of affluence among the peer clique to engage in embezzling and tax evasion or to take or give bribe so as to be approved of or accepted.

Peer groups or associations have their own cultures, sanctions or rituals into which members are socialized and accordingly, members (especially new members) who do not comply with any of these may be ostracized (Carlson, 2010). Peer pressure extends to all groups. A peer group refers to persons that belong to the same age (or about the same age) and/or status. Examples of peer groups include, age peer group, school or educational peer group, social peer group, professional peer group and work peer group.

2.4.3 Family Background and Stealing among Youths

Stealing can take various forms and kinds; it can be robbery, forgery, plagiarism, evading taxation, infidelity, depriving (someone) of something belonging or due and embezzlement (Chumbe, Sarah, Martha and Helen, 2013). Stealing is an old and common problem in the history of mankind implied in the Holy Bible as early as in the times of Abraham and his son Isaac. People globally steal from each other, in families and in institutions. In USA, a study done on attitudes and conduct of some 29, 760 high school students by Josephson Institute found out that an average of 30% of students admitted to have stolen from a store within the past year (Josephson institute of Ethic, 2009). Subair (1999) in his research reported that stealing was among the three most frequently committed crimes among secondary school students in Botswana. In Kenya, stealing among secondary school students rated very high among the common indiscipline problems as reported by teachers in sampled schools; it accounted for 85% as reported by respondent students and second (81%) in the order of severity (Mbugu, 2005)

The lifetime prevalence of stealing appears fairly high. A recent, large epidemiological study of adults found that 11.3% of the general population admitted to having shoplifted in their lifetimes (Blanco, Grant and Petry, 2008). This finding is consistent with estimates by the National Association of Shoplifting Prevention (2009) that 1 in 11 (9.1%) people have shoplifted during their lifetime. Stealing in adults has been associated with other antisocial behaviors, psychiatric comorbidity (e.g., substance use disorders, pathological gambling, and bipolar disorder), and impaired psychosocial functioning. Stealing appears to start generally in childhood or adolescence, with approximately 66% of individuals who reported lifetime stealing beginning before age 15 years.

Family background affects the development of youths. According to Chumbe, Sarah, Martha and Helen (2013), children who come from families who have the vice of stealing are likely to carry over the same behavior in later life. In their study, all principals and four out of six teacher counselors revealed that family background was one of the causes of stealing in schools. From the students 110 students who were 73% of the sampled students were of the view that family background was the cause of stealing in the sampled schools.

2.4.4 Influence of Educational Attainment on Illicit Drug Use among Youths

Illicit drug use among youth is a pressing public health problem at the national, community, and school level (Johnston et al. 2002; U.S. Department of Justice 2001). In United State for example, rates of use have increased considerably since 1991, when about 12 percent of 10th grade students and 16 percent of 12th grade students reported any illicit drug use in the past month. As of 2002, 21 percent of 10th grade students and 25 percent of 12th grade students reported past month illicit drug use (Johnston et al. 2002). The recent increase in illicit drug use among youth has led to concern about both the short-term and the long-term consequences of this risky behavior (ONDCP 2003). Some of the commonly abuse illicit substance among Nigeria youths are cannabis and methamphetamine

Social researchers are particularly interested in knowing what factors motivate youths to use illicit drug. Many literature that examine the relationship between illicit drug use and educational attainment had done so analyzing only how illicit drug use obstruct academic performance, especially amon adolescents (Chatterji, 2006). However, there are rarely any study on how educational attainment impact on involvement in use of illicit drug, especially among.

According to Psacharapoulos (2007), there is a link between low educational attainment among adolescents that drops out of school and use of illicit drugs. Bachman, O'Malley and Johnston (1980) use a composite measure of parents' educational attainment, which serves as a rough indicator of family socioeconomic status (SES). The result of the measure shows relatively little correlation with the four drug use measures. The largest association with parental education is a correlation of 0.16 with alcohol use by females, which contrasts with a correlation of only .04 for males. Since males in general average higher in alcohol use than females, this means that in families with higher parental education the drinking patterns of male and female high school seniors are not so widely different, whereas in families with less parental education the female seniors drink distinctly less than the males.

Put another way, there is a very slight interaction between parental education and sex of the respondent in predicting illicit drug use; and the nature of that interaction suggests that lower socioeconomic status seniors may experience a stronger drinking. "double standard" concerning.

A similar, though weaker, difference in male and female correlations appears in the relationships between parental education and marijuana use ($r = -.08$ for females; $r = .02$ for males).

2.4.5 Employment Status and Thuggery among Youths

Thuggery is simply rough and an act of violent behaviour. Common forms of thuggery in Nigeria are political thuggery and land thuggery. Political thuggery is defined as an act of violence or behaviour by ruffians hired or instigated by politicians to intimidate their opponents. It is therefore safe to say that thuggery in Nigerian politics is a means to an end (Anzaki, 2017). The Nigerian political scene has experienced violence and thuggery in varying degrees. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2004) defines violence as the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person or against a group or community that either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, mal-development or deprivation. The definition is all encompassing; it covers a wide range of acts, going beyond physical acts to include threats and intimidation. Besides death and injury, the definition also includes the myriad and often less obvious consequences of violent behaviour, such as psychological harm, deprivation and mal-development that compromise the well-being of individuals, families and communities. The definition particularly covers electoral violence, which is part and parcel of political conflict or political violence.

Majority of those that perpetrate the act political thuggery in Nigeria are youths in their productive years and with promising futures given enabling political, economic and social environments. They are employed informally to serve the interest of desperate politicians who in the course of furthering their political ambitions engage their service. Political thuggery has remained an “obstacle” to competitive electoral politics in Nigeria. The act of thuggery is more evident in urban cities like Lagos despite the fact that the act is prohibited by law. For example, the Lagos State Environmental Law 2012 prohibits all forms of thuggery, touting, and extortion. However, the act of thuggery continues to flourish in Lagos.

Unemployment and violent crime, including thuggery, are always thought to work hand in hand, with an increase in one leading to a rise in the other, and vice versa. While such opinion is popular among the general public, many scholars (e.g. Moreoff, 1997) have disputed a direct relationship between unemployment and homicide perpetration. However, there seem to be a general consensus

that the phenomenon of youth unemployment is devastating to both the individual and the society as a whole both psychologically and economically. Unemployment causes frustration, dejection, desperation and dependency on family members and friends who also have their own problems to contend with (Adebayo, 2013).As such it can be logically deduced that there is at least an indirect relationship between unemployment and thuggery.

The magnitude of the danger which youth unemployment poses to the society is better understood when, according to Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010), over 64 million youths are unemployed and 1.6 million are under-employed. According to National Bureau of Statistics (2010), the national unemployment rates for Nigeria between 2000 and 2009 showed that the number of unemployed persons constituted 13.1% in 2000; 13.6% in 2001; 12.6% in 2002; 14.8% in 2003; 13.4% in 2004; 11.9% in 2005; 13.7% in 2006; 14.6% in 2007; 14.9% in 2008 and 19.4% in 2009. As regards the age group, the report shows that as at March 2009 in Nigeria, for persons between the 15 and 24 years, 41.6% were unemployed; persons between 25 and 44 years, 17% were unemployed. Furthermore, for those with only primary education, 14.8% were unemployed, and for those with only secondary education, 23.8% were unemployed; while for those with tertiary education, 21.3% were unemployed. For those who never attended school and those below primary education, 21.0 and 22.3% were unemployed respectively.

The scariest undertone of Nigeria's socio-economic underachievement, by far, is the steady rise in youth crime, nurtured in a climate of increasing national income and the simultaneous failure of employment-generation and poverty alleviation programmes. This precarious situation has left the youths in a vicious cycle of poverty that daily erodes their confidence and bright future. The frustration and desperation that daily torments the unemployed creates a fertile ground for crime to thrive. The frequent report of mortality resulting from intimate partner violence in various national dailies suggests homicide may be on the increase in Nigeria.

2.5 Summary and Conclusion

This review has examined the concept of crime from both legal and social perspectives. Urbanization process and its relationship with crime is also examined. A critical look at literature shows that shows that there is variation in speed of urbanization between developed and developing nations. The speed of urbanization is faster and it is often unplanned in developing

nation than in developed nations. Economic reason has been identified as the major reasons why young people migrate from rural to urban areas. More often than not, young people migrate to urban area in search for employment opportunity and with the expectation of seeing a “greener pasture” in urban cities, however; this expectation is often unmet. Rather, they encounter a new life where cost of living is much higher or rather difficult than that of their experience back in rural areas. Hence, the rapid pace of urbanization in developing regions like Africa is occurring within the context of macroeconomic stability and growth across many countries in the regions. Therefore, many of them may resolve to committing crime in order to survive.

The extent to which young people are involved was also examined. A critical review of literature shows that while public opinion and media reports often suggest that youths are the major perpetrators of urban crime, there is dispute among scholars on the extent to which youths are involved in crime, especially when compared to older population. While some studies suggest that youths are more involved in urban crime, some studies dispute this finding. However, there is a consensus among researcher that youths are more susceptible to certain factors that may increase the probability of engaging in criminal activities. Some of the factors identified include: family disruption, drug and alcohol abuse, limited economic opportunities and unemployment.

Finally, the review examined the relationship between various socio-environmental factors and urban criminal activities. Some of the socio-environmental factors that were examined include place of residents, peer group pressure, family background, educational attainment and employment status. These factors and their impact on urban criminal activities such as street fighting, vandalization of government utilities, stealing, illicit drugs use and thuggery were discussed extensively in this review.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to link this study to earlier model and explanation in terms of explanations and interpretations which have been offered for observed relationship between socio-environmental factors and urban crime among youths. This study adopted sociological theoretical approach that involves integration of criminological theories to explain relationship between variables under investigation. This approach has been dominant in the investigation on the trends of urban crime. However, economic approaches are also presently used in the discussion of crime but are however over the scope of the present study. Beginning in the early twentieth century, theories about the causes of crime began to move away from biological and psychological causes of human behavior toward social environment explanations, such as slum life and the society at large (Gelles and Levine, 1999). The most prominent and influential sociological theories of crime and delinquency today have their roots in the schools of thought beginning at the turn of the twentieth century; most modern theories are, in essence, repackaged and polished versions of earlier theories designed to explain the political and social turmoil of the 1960s and 1970s (Lilly, Cullen, and Ball, 1989).

3.2 Social Disorganization Theory

Social disorganization theory indicates how structurally disadvantaged neighborhoods, characterized by high levels of poverty, unemployment, single-parent households, racial and ethnic heterogeneity, and residential mobility are likely to have higher rates of crime (Sampson, 1997; Shaw and McKay, 1942). Thus, neighborhood researchers often hypothesize that neighborhood structural disadvantage gives rise to social processes that lead to neighborhood disorganization and higher rates of youth problem behavior. Although these social problems tend to be worse in neighborhoods characterized as highly disadvantaged, some studies find that even among neighborhoods with high levels of structural disadvantage, there is substantial variation on these outcome measures (Elliott, Menard, Rankin, and Elliott, 2006; Esbensen and Huizinga, 1990). For instance, neighborhoods characterized as highly disadvantaged on the basis of their social structure

do not always exhibit high crime rates. This finding suggests that there may be significant variation in social processes operating within structurally disadvantaged neighborhoods.

The origins of social disorganization theory date back to the early 1900s. Two researchers from the University of Chicago, Clifford Shaw and Henry McKay (1929), began a series of studies using official records which showed that in the city of Chicago, rates of criminality, delinquency and commitment to correctional institutions varied markedly by area. In particular, rates were highest in slums near the city center and diminished as distance from the center of the city increased, except in areas of industry and commerce just outside of the central district, which had some of the highest rates. Shaw and McKay also found that rates of crime and delinquency exhibited a remarkable consistent patterning over many decades; in particular, the spatial pattern of rates revealed significant long-term stability even though the nationality structure of the population in the inner-city areas changed greatly over time. Shaw and McKay, thus, determined that crime and delinquency were not the result of personal characteristics of the residents who lived in the neighborhoods but were tied to the neighborhoods themselves. Since areas of high and low crime and delinquency maintained their relative positions over many years, a key theoretical task became to explain the existence and stability of these area differentials over time.

A fundamental part of their explanation involved the concept of social disorganization. Social disorganization refers to the inability of a community to realize the common values of its members and maintain effective social controls. As Kornhauser (1978) describes, "Social disorganization exists in the first instance when the structure and culture of a community are incapable of implementing and expressing the values of its own residents." According to the theory, a common value among neighborhood residents is the desire for a crime-free community. In essence, then, socially disorganized neighborhoods are ineffective in combating crime. A socially organized community is characterized by (1) solidarity, or an internal consensus on essential norms and values (e.g., residents want and value the same things, such as a crime-free neighborhood); (2) cohesion, or a strong bond among neighbors (e.g., residents know and like one another); and (3) integration, with social interaction occurring on a regular basis (e.g., residents spend time with one another). Conversely, a disorganized community has little solidarity among residents and lacks social cohesion or integration.

Perhaps the greatest difference between socially organized and disorganized neighborhoods is the levels of informal social control in those neighborhoods. Informal social control is defined as the scope of collective intervention that the community directs toward local problems, including crime (Kornhauser, 1978; Shaw and McKay, 1942). It is the informal, nonofficial actions taken by residents to combat crime in their communities, such as, for example, when residents question persons about suspicious activity or admonish misbehaving youth and inform parents of their children's misconduct. In essence, residents act as the "eyes and ears" of the community and their informal surveillance, and even simple presence, deters others from engaging in crime.

According to the theory, socially disorganized neighborhoods have lower levels of informal social control, and thus experience higher crime rates when compared to more socially organized neighborhoods. Ecological characteristics of neighborhoods influence the degree of social disorganization in the community. This is because certain characteristics can impede the development of social ties that promote the ability to solve common problems, including crime. Ecological characteristics of greatest interest to social disorganization researchers include poverty, joblessness, population mobility or turnover, racial composition, and family disruption, among others. Although community characteristics such as poverty or residential instability are related to crime, these factors themselves do not directly cause crime, according to the theory. That is, ecological characteristics are related to crime only indirectly through various neighborhood processes such as informal social control. As such, poverty, residential instability, and other ecological characteristics are important in as much as they affect the mediating processes of social disorganization.

In light of the above discussion, Sampson (1987, p.34) describes the processes by which neighborhood characteristics and crime are associated:

Neighborhood characteristics such as family disorganization, residential mobility, and structural density weaken informal social control networks; informal social controls are impeded by weak local social bonds, lowered community attachment, anonymity, and reduced capacity for surveillance and guardianship; other factors such as poverty and racial composition also probably affect informal control, although their influence is in all likelihood indirect; residents in areas characterized by family disorganization, mobility,

and building density are less able to perform guardianship activities, less likely to report general deviance to authorities, to intervene in public disturbances, and to assume responsibility for supervision of youth activities; the result is that deviance is tolerated and public norms of social control are not effective.

For youth with weak bonds to conventional society, the social reinforcement provided by the delinquent peer group increases the likelihood of sustained criminal behavior. Neighborhoods are also expected to vary according to the opportunities they provide youth for achieving delinquent or conventional goals (Cloward and Ohlin, 1960; De Coster, Heimer, and Wittrock, 2006; Haynie, Silver, and Teasdale, 2006). The social structure (poverty, single-parent households, racial and ethnic heterogeneity, and residential mobility) and social processes (weak social networks and low levels of collective efficacy) that characterize disorganized neighborhoods also contribute to the presence of delinquent opportunity structures and an absence of conventional opportunity structures for youth.

While limited research exists on the relationship between neighborhood social structure, social processes and delinquent opportunity structures, recent studies examining these variables suggest that neighborhood disadvantage influences delinquency indirectly by increasing exposure to criminogenic street context (De Coster, Heimer, and Wittrock, 2006) and opportunities for involvement with delinquent peer groups (Haynie, Silver, and Teasdale, 2006). Structurally disadvantaged neighborhoods that lack the resources to effectively monitor children and provide few sanctions for inappropriate behavior are likely to have a higher number of delinquent peer groups available to youth (Cloward and Ohlin, 1960; Sampson, 1997; Sampson and Groves, 1989). Also, the social networks between parents and the parents of their children's friends who allow parents to monitor their children's activities tend to be deficient in structurally disadvantaged neighborhoods. Poorly monitored youth are more likely to socialize with deviant peers and to engage in misconduct (Henry, Tolan, and Gorman-Smith, 2001; Larzelere and Patterson, 1990; Patterson and Stouthamer-Loeber, 1984).

Due to their limited resources, disadvantaged neighborhoods are also expected to provide limited conventional opportunities, including exposure to social networks modeling

conventional success. Youth in advantaged neighborhoods usually have opportunities that poor children lack, such as summer camps, music lessons, sports training, home computers, and special tutoring, whereas disadvantaged neighborhoods have few public resources that support the developmental needs of youth and their families.

3.2.1 Limitation and Criticisms of Social disorganization Theory

Given the primitive nature of data analysis during the early 1900s, it is not surprising that scholars were unable to conduct sophisticated analyses that would allow them to fully test social disorganization theory's arguments. Early Chicago school theorists "tested" the theory by plotting the spatial distribution of crime in the city to determine whether it was consistent with the theory's predictions, and then correlated characteristics of neighborhoods with crime rates. Studies were able to document, for example, that poor, mobile, and racially heterogeneous neighborhoods had the highest crime rates but they could not specify the mechanisms (e.g., social ties, informal social control) accounting for this relationship. This was problematic, in part, because it did not allow researchers to rule out competing theoretical explanations such as strain, which also theorize a poverty-crime association.

Even decades after the early work of Chicago School researchers, little progress had been made in this area. Studies included the "front end" of social disorganization models, that is, attributes of the community, as well as the "back end" or crime and delinquency outcomes, but continued to leave out the crucial middle, or indicators reflecting how much social disorganization is occurring in a neighborhood (Kubrin, Stucky, and Krohn, 2009). Cohen (1955) believed that the social disorganization theory was only one sided. It was only relevant when explaining cases of delinquency or crime by asserting that there were no societal constraints. However, the theory could not explain how this came about; what were the pressures that caused individuals to exhibit deviant behaviour. Merton (1957) believes that a satisfactory theory was one that examined both sides of the coin; i.e. those who committed crimes and those who did not.

3.3 General Strain Theory

Robert Agnew (1999) proposed a general strain theory which is the best known contemporary version. Unlike its predecessor, Durkheim, argued that crime was as a result of the inability of individual to achieve monetary-success, middle-class status or both, Agnew's GST theory is much

broader and uses the individuals' environment to explain their participation in crime. GST focuses on three major types of strain. Following classic strain theory, the first type is the "failure to achieve positively valued goals". In addition, GST focuses on the "loss of positively valued stimuli" and the "presentation of noxious or negatively valued stimuli". The loss of positively valued stimuli includes a potentially wide range of negative events or experiences, including the theft of valued property and the withdrawal of parental love. The presentation of noxious stimuli also includes a wide range of negative experiences, such as parental abuse, bullying from peers, and criminal victimization. Literally hundreds of strains fall into these three broad categories.

Agnew argues that these strains may lead to anger, frustration and other affective states that create a pressure for corrective action that may include criminal activity. Literally hundreds of strains fall into these three broad categories. General strain theory states that certain of these strains are more likely to result in crime than others. These include strains that are high in magnitude (severe, frequent, of long duration, high in centrality), are seen as unjust, are associated with low social control, and can be readily resolved through crime. Such strains include parental rejection and abuse; harsh or excessive parental discipline; marital problems, such as conflict and abuse; negative school experiences, such as failing grades and negative relations with teachers; abusive peer relations; criminal victimization; the inability to legally satisfy strong desires for "fast cash," thrills/excitement, and masculine status; persistent unemployment or underemployment; and racial discrimination. The lack of opportunities has also been well documented as contributing to individuals' participation in crime. Agnew (1992) argued the prospect that group differences (gender, age, education and employment status) might play a role in the types of strains individuals frequently encounter.

Research suggests that most of these strains have relatively large effects on crime, particularly violence, although more research is needed on the impact of these strains (Agnew, 2006). Agnew explained further that young people in inner-city communities are especially likely to experience most of these strains, highlighting the relevance of GST to the explanation of urban youth violence. As noted, urban youth experience extraordinarily high levels of violent victimization and other exposure to violence. They also experience high levels of family disruption, abuse and neglect, school problems, marital problems, poverty and inequality; unemployment and underemployment; and difficulty in legally achieving monetary and status goals. In addition, urban youth experience

much class and racial/ ethnic discrimination, including negative experiences with the police and other representatives of the larger society (Kubrin 2005; Stewart and Simons 2006).

Further, GST highlights unique processes that operate at the community level (Agnew 1999). Given the strains they experience, disadvantaged communities tend to possess a relatively large number of angry, frustrated individuals. Also, the residents of such communities, particularly the youth, spend more time in public places, such as the street. This results from their higher levels of unemployment and school dropout, more crowded housing, relative lack of air-conditioning, and high density of inner-city communities. These facts increase the likelihood that residents will encounter angry and potentially hostile individuals; and that such individuals will encounter one another, thereby contributing to elevated levels of crime and violence (Brezina, Piquero, and Mazerolle 2001).

However, the choice of delinquent versus non-delinquent adaptations is said to be influenced by various conditioning factors. For example, deviant attitudes, deviant peers, external attributions, self-esteem and self-efficacy that buffer one from strain or increase one's disposition for criminal behavior. The research examining GST has been generally supportive, though support for the conditioning effects has been more limited.

In sum, GST explains the high levels of urban violence partly in terms of the greater exposure of urban youth to a range of strains conducive to crime. General strain theory is distinguished from other theories by the central role that it assigns to these strains or negative social relations. Certain of these strains, such as parental abuse and unemployment, are considered by other theories because they also contribute to low control and the social learning of crime. But other strains, such as criminal victimization and discrimination, have been neglected by other theories. And GST is the only theory to focus on the full range of strains or negative relations.

3.3.1 Limitation and Criticism of General Strain Theory

Most of the empirical work on GST also suffers because it has been limited to samples of fairly conventional school-age adolescents (Baron and Hartnagel, 2002; Hagan and McCarthy, 1997; Piquero and Sealock, 2004). Agnew (2001) is one of the critics of his own work. Recently, Agnew reviewed the body of work testing GST and concluded that previous research is severely limited because it suffers from two particular problems. First, he observes that many of the key measures of strain outlined in the GST, including certain measures of goal blockage and certain types of negative treatment, are absent. Therefore, there is little information on whether these types of strain

are linked to criminal behavior. Second, he notes that most research on GST examines the effect of a single, cumulative measure of strain on delinquency.' Despite once advocating this approach, Agnew suggests that the use of such cumulative measures masks the effects of individual strain measures. He stresses that an examination of different types of strain outside of a cumulative index is needed to reveal which forms of strain have a strong impact on crime and which do not.

3.4 Differential Association Theory

Sutherland and Cressey (1955) built on the Shaw and McKay observation about the transmission of delinquent values from one generation to the next whereby crime is learned through social interaction by noting the importance of “differential social organization” to account for the observation that social groups are arranged differently (some organized in support of criminal activity and others organized against it). Sutherland advanced the theory that criminal behavior is learned through social interactions wherein opportunities that are favorable to the violation of the law differs from opportunities that are unfavorable to violation of the law for someone who embraces crime as an acceptable way of life. He proposed that an excess of definition conducive for criminality could be learned by individuals and his theory has been seen as particularly useful in explaining juvenile gang crime and white crime, though it is not without critics.

Sutherland's theory of differential association is essentially a theory of learning. It states that criminal behavior is learned from contact with those who maintain criminal attitudes and practices. "The process of learning criminal behavior is by association with criminal and anti-criminal patterns" (Jeffrey, 1959). He explained further that "Systematic criminal behavior is determined by the process of associating with those who commit crimes. Sutherland (1949) described this theory as “differential association.” He maintained that his theories of differential association and differential social organization were compatible and together formed a comprehensive explanation of crime.

Differential association explained why any given individual was drawn into crime; differential social disorganization explained why rates of crime were higher in certain sectors of American society. Deviance was the result of socialization and learning values of a subculture that supports attitudes and behaviors that the mainstream culture rejects (Sutherland and Cressey, 1955). Most provocatively, Sutherland's theory applied to all strata of society and was able to account for the offenses “committed by a person of respectability and high social status in the course of his

occupation''. In describing crimes committed in the areas of business, politics, and the professions, Sutherland coined the term "white-collar crime".

3.4.1 Limitation and Criticism of Differential Association Theory

Jeffrey (1959) pointed to the following criticisms that can be made of the theory of differential association: 1). the theory does not explain the origin of criminality, since criminality has to exist before it can be learned by someone else. Why the first criminal act? 2). the theory does not explain crimes of passion or accident. 3). the theory does not explain crimes by those with no prior contact with criminals or criminal attitudes. 4). It does not explain the case of the non-criminal living in a criminal environment. 5). the theory does not differentiate between criminal and non-criminal behavior, since both types of behavior can be learned. A person can become a dentist or a Catholic as a result of differential association. 6). it does not take into account the psychological factor referred to as motivation or "differential response pattern." 7). the theory does not account for the differential rate of crime associated with age, sex, urban areas, and minority groups. Why do males commit more crimes than females, or why do Negroes commit more crimes than non-Negroes? Why are criminal patterns concentrated in certain groups and not in others? It is no answer to say that these groups are criminalistic because they associate with criminal patterns, since what we are trying to explain in the first place is the existence of criminal patterns in these groups. What is there about being a male, or a member of a minority group, or living in a slum area that produces a high crime rate? Sutherland's theory does not explain the origin of crime rates; rather it explains how a person comes into contact with criminality.

3.5 Opportunity Theory

Cloward and Ohlin (1960) formulated opportunity theory. They were former students of Merton and Sutherland, respectively, and thus incorporated and expanded on both differential association theory and strain theory. Cloward and Ohlin built on the work of Merton and Cohen by advancing the idea that youths in slum areas lacked the legitimate means and opportunities to be successful and acquire status. They also expanded on Sutherland's work on cultural transmission and concluded that criminal behavior depended upon access to requisite illegitimate means. However, unlike Cohen who stated that delinquent subcultures take on values that are oppositional to those of the main culture.

Cloward and Ohlin suggested that lower-class delinquents are proactive and goal-oriented by seizing available opportunities even though most of them are illegitimate. According to Cloward and Ohlin's (1960) opportunity theory, delinquent subcultures emerge and persist in lower-class areas where there are enough youths to band together and support one another against their remoteness and estrangement from conventional values, in pursuit of illegitimate opportunities that exceed the number of legitimate opportunities for success. As illegitimate opportunities for success are distributed through society as unevenly as the legitimate opportunities for success, the types of delinquent subcultures are determined by the type of neighborhood and illegitimate opportunities available (Shoemaker, 1996). Shoemaker states further that neighborhoods that are stable and share conventional and unconventional systems are marked by criminal/theft gangs; neighborhoods characterized by transience, instability, and an absence of criminal organizations are marked by conflict/violent gangs; and neighborhoods that could be either type but wherein members have not been successful in both the legitimate and illegitimate worlds are marked by retreatist/drug-user gangs.

Summarily, opportunity theory postulates that opportunities play a role in causing all crime; crime opportunities are highly specific; crime opportunities are concentrated in time and space; crime opportunities depend on everyday movements; one crime produces opportunities for another; some products offer more tempting crime opportunities; social and technological changes produce new crime opportunities; opportunities for crime can be reduced; reducing opportunities does not usually displace crime; focused opportunity reduction can produce wider declines in crime.

3.5.1 Criticism of Opportunity Theory

The theory has been criticized for denying the influence of the "root causes" of crime such as unemployment, maternal deprivation, subculture, relative deprivation and anomie, which criminologists had so patiently documented over the years.

3.6 CONCLUSION

A critical examination of the sociological theories is crucial to having an in-depth understanding of how socio-environmental factors impact on urban crime among youths. The general strain theory examined three types of strain which include "loss of positively valued stimuli" and the "presentation of noxious or negatively valued stimuli". The theory posits that frustration that

follows these strains may serve as foundation for involvement in crime, and that some of these strains are feature of certain urban location.

Social disorganization theory found evidence regarding the impact of neighborhood subculture on crime and delinquency. Of particular interest is their finding that areas of low economic status were characterized by diversity in norms and standards of behavior, rather than uniformity (recall that solidarity, or an internal consensus on norms and values, is critical for social organization). Shaw and McKay found that in poor communities, youth were exposed to a wide variety of contradictory (and sometimes unlawful) standards rather than to a relatively consistent and conventional pattern of norms. Sutherland's differential association theory posit that criminal behaviour is learned in the same way as law-abiding values are learned, and that, this learning activity is accomplished, in interactions with others, through a process of communication within intimate groups. He argues that, just as one can be socialized into good behaviour, so also can one be socialized into bad behavior. However, due to socio-environmental factors, some individuals may be exposed to deviant behavior than others.

Lastly, opportunity theory that offenders are most likely to commit crimes when they perceive the effort and risk to be relatively low, and the associated rewards to be relatively high. Offenders make rational choices and thus choose targets that offer a high reward with little effort and risk. The occurrence of a crime depends on two things: the presence of at least one motivated offender who is ready or willing to engage in a crime, and the conditions of the environment in which that offender is situated, to wit, opportunities for crime. All crimes require opportunity but not every opportunity is followed by crime. Similarly a motivated offender is necessary for the commission of a crime but not sufficient. Hence, the theory provides guideline for understanding of how socio-environmental factors influence urban crime among youths.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH METHOD

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents information concerning the techniques that was adopted in conducting this study. It explains the procedure that was followed in an attempt to achieve the study objectives and answer the research questions, and the philosophy that underpins the researcher's view of research. Also, it deals with the various methods and tools the researcher employs in collection and analysis of data and evaluating and making conclusion of results. These include; research design, study location, study population, sampling technique and size, method of data collection, research instrument, method of data analysis and what ethical considerations were involved in the study.

4.2 Research Design

Research design encompasses the methodology and procedures employed to conduct research. A research needs a design or a structure before data collection or analysis can commence. It gives an explanation for researcher's logical model of proof. In other words, it explains how the researcher hopes to establish relationship between the variables under study. For the purpose of this study, mixed method (triangulation method) approach was adopted in order to broaden the understanding of the research problem. According to Creswell (2009), "mixed methods have procedures that employ aspects of both quantitative and qualitative techniques". The importance of doing this is to broaden understanding by incorporating both qualitative and quantitative research, or to use one approach to better understand, explain, or build on the results from other approaches. Hence, this study employed both qualitative and quantitative research approach. Quantitative research focuses on numbers or quantities. Quantitative research involves collecting and converting data into numerical form so that statistical calculations can be made and conclusions drawn, while qualitative research is concerned with qualitative phenomenon, and the socially constructed nature of reality. Essentially, qualitative research is about recording, analysing and attempting to uncover the deeper meaning and significance of human behaviour and experience, including contradictory beliefs, behaviours and emotions. Researchers are interested in gaining a rich and complex understanding of people's experience.

4.3 Study Location

The study location for this study was Lagos State, Southwestern Nigeria. The State has the smallest landmass when compared to other states in Nigeria yet; it has the highest urban population, which is 27.4 % of the national estimate (UN-Habitat, 2006). According to the 2006 National Census, Lagos State has a population of 9,013,534 in relation to the National count of 140,003,542. However, based on the UN-Habitat and international development agencies' estimates, Lagos State is said to have about 24.6 million inhabitants in 2015. Of this population, Metropolitan Lagos accounts for over 85% on an area that is 37% of the land area of the State, and the fact that Lagos population is growing 10 times faster than that of New York and Los Angeles, and more than the population of 32 African nations combined, the State population is expected to hit the 35 million mark in 2020. Lagos State was created on May 27, 1967 by virtue of Decree No. 14 of 1967 which restructured Nigeria's Federation into 12 States.

However, this study was limited to two local government areas in the state (Mushin and Eti Osa Local Government Areas). These locations were selected using a combination of stratified and purposive technique. Stratified technique was used to divide Lagos into two main strata: Mainland and Island Lagos on the basis of socioeconomic and environmental attributes rather than strictly geographically or administratively defined locations. Thereafter, purposive technique was used to select Mushin and Eti-Osa. The selection of these locations was considered suitable to capture the scope of the study and answers research questions of the study because the two selected local government areas represent two sides of an urban city.

Mushin to a large extent is a low-income area characterized with high population density and poor infrastructure. On the other hand, most of the elite areas in Lagos, including Ikoyi and Lekki Peninsulas, are located in Eti-Osa Local Government Area. Hence, these study locations gave this study advantage of doing comparative analysis of socio-environmental factors in order to draw a logical conclusion on the impacts of these factors on urban crime among youths.

Mushin is located 10 km north of the city core, adjacent to the main road to Ikeja, and is largely a congested residential area with inadequate sanitation and low-quality housing. It had 633,009 inhabitants at the 2006 Census. After the 1960 independence from Great Britain, there was large migration to the suburban areas. This led to intensive overcrowding. As a result, poor sanitation

and inadequate housing lead to poor living conditions. However, since the rise of industrialization in Nigeria, Mushin has become one of the largest beneficiaries of the industrial expansion. Their local commercial enterprises include spinning and weaving of cotton, shoe manufacturing, bicycle and motorized-cycle assembly, along with the production of powdered milk.

Eti-osa Local Government Area on the other hand was the federal capital of Nigeria before the national capital was moved to Abuja. Within Eti-Osa are several important areas of Lagos State, including Lagos' Victoria Island and Lekki port. The area to a large extent is an elite area with some of the best infrastructures in the state.

4.4 Study Population

A research population is a well-defined collection of individuals or objects known to have similar characteristics. All individuals or objects within a certain population usually have a common, binding characteristic or trait. For the purpose of this study, youths (both male and female) between the ages of 18-35, who reside in Mushin and Eti-Osa, were the population of interest. For the key informant interview, police officers who have been serving in Lagos State for at least three years were selected in the study area, and constituted part of the study population for this study.

4.5 Sampling Techniques and Sampling Size

Sampling is the statistical process of selecting a subset (called a “sample”) of a population of interest for purposes of making observations and statistical inferences about that population. Social work research is generally about inferring patterns of behaviors within specific populations. We cannot study entire populations because of feasibility and cost constraints, and hence, we must select a representative sample from the population of interest for observation and analysis.

This study adopted both probability and non-probability sampling techniques to select respondents for this study. Probability technique is a sampling technique in which every unit in the population has a chance (non-zero probability) of being selected in the sample, and this chance can be accurately determined, non-probability is a sampling technique in which some units of the population have zero chance of selection or where the probability of selection cannot be accurately determined. In furtherance to this, the multi-stage sampling technique and simple random technique was used to select 300 respondents. At the first stage of the multi-stage sampling, the

selected areas were divided into political constituency. Mushin and Eti-Osa have two (2) constituencies each. At the second stage, the constituency was divided into wards. Mushin has 14 political wards (Alakara, Idi-oro/Odi-olowo, Babalosa; Ojuwoye; Ilupeju; Olateju; Kayode/Fadeyi; Ilupeju/Industrial; Mushin/Atewolara; Papa Ajao; Ilasamaja; Babalosa/Idi-Araba; Itire and Idi-Araba), while Eti-Osa has a total of 10 wards (Victoria I, Victoria Island II; Ilasan Housing Estate/Maiyegun; Ikota/Ikate Village; Igbo-Efon/Ikota Housing Estate; Ajah Village; Addo Village; Ikoyi I; Ikoyi II; and Obalende). Two wards were purposively selected from each of the selected local government areas. Ojuwoye and Idi-oro/Odi-Olowo wards were selected from Mushin wards while Ikoyi I and Igbo efon/mayegun were selected from Eti-osa. From each of the selected wards, 75 respondents were selected using stratified random technique. The stratification here was based on age because only respondents between the ages of 18-35 were selected.

Therefore, the sample size comprised a total of 300 respondents within the ages of 18-35. This size was selected because there is no reliable statistics of the total number of youth in the area. Hence, survey questionnaire was administered to generate quantitative data from them. For the qualitative data, simple random technique, which involved the use of lottery method, was used to select 2 police stations in the areas under study. From these police stations, 4 police officers (2 from each of the police station) were selected as key informants for the study.

4.6 Data Collection

Both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection were adopted in this study. Quantitative data was collected through structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was self-administered. Qualitative data was collected in a face-to-face interview with selected police officers through the use of semi-structured interview guide that contained questions designed in an open-ended format. This is because one-on-one interview with individual respondents enables researchers (interviewers) to establish rapport with respondents and also have much more opportunity to ask follow-up questions, probe for additional information, and circle back to key questions later on in the interview to generate a rich understanding of variables under study.

4.7 Research Instruments

Research instruments are tools for data collection on variables of interest. The research instruments that were utilized in this study to gather data are questionnaire and interview guide. The questionnaire featured questions that captured the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents as well objectives of the study. The questionnaire was divided into sections based on the themes of research objectives. In-depth Interview (I.D.I) guide was also used to collect qualitative data. An in-depth interview guide is a written list of questions on topics that need to be covered. The In-depth interview guide was used because it offers the opportunity to obtain deep and rich information from the research participants in order to answer research questions of the study effectively.

4.8 Methods of Data Analysis

Raw data collected from the field was analyzed for the purpose of drawing conclusions regarding the research questions of interest. Firstly, recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim. An attempt was made to identify various themes and data analysis was followed. The analysis focused on content analysis. Results from each research question and their themes were summarized with direct quotations from the participants' responses. Chi-square analysis was carried out on the data with the aid Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) in order to examine relationship between variables under study.

4.9 Ethical Considerations

Ethical issues in social work research are of great importance because social work research deals with human subject. There are rules that govern how scientific research is carried out with stated code of conduct that helps in guiding the researcher in the course of the research study without implicating the respondents who take part in the study. The right of the respondents must be respected and they must not be subjected to any adverse condition due to their participation in a study. Hence, respondents were duly informed of the purpose of the study and what it entailed before they participated in it. Also, their anonymity of the respondents was ensured. Respondents were also informed that they could cease from participating at any point in time during the interview without any consequence.

CHAPTER FIVE

DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter is concerned with organization, presentation, analysis and interpretation of quantitative and qualitative data collected in order to test research hypotheses and answer research questions. For the purpose of this study, a total of 300 questionnaires were distributed to 150 youths in Eti-osa local government area of Lagos and another 150 youths in Mushin local government area. Hence, data collected from the sample of respondent (n=300) youths were analyzed and interpreted in a descriptive form. The quantitative data is backed with qualitative data obtained through Key informant interview from 4 police officers in order to gain in-depth understanding of the problem and draw a logical conclusion. The result is summarized below in the corresponding tables and charts and supported with verbatim quotations obtained from key informants' responses.

5.2 SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Table 5.1: Distribution of respondents by sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	171	57.0
Female	129	43.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.1 above shows the distribution of respondents by sex. The table reveals that majority of the respondents were males. More precisely, the table indicates that 171 (57.0%) of the respondents were males, while 129 (43.0%) were females.

Table 5.2: Distribution of respondents by ethnic group

Ethnic group	Frequency	Percent
Yoruba	147	49.0
Igbo	100	33.3
Hausa/Fulani	9	3.0

Other	44	14.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.2 above shows the distribution of respondents according to their ethnic background. The table indicates that 147 (49.0%) of the respondents were Yorubas, 100 (33.3%) of the respondents were Igbo, 9 (3.0%) were Hausa/Fulani, while 44 (14.7%) were from other smaller ethnic group such as Idoma, Isoko, Efik, Ijaw, Epira, Tapa among others. The figure indicates that majority of the respondents were Yoruba. This may be due to the fact that the study was carried out in Lagos State, South-West Nigeria which is predominantly occupied by Yoruba.

Chart 5.1: Distribution of respondents by religion

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in chart 5.1 above capture respondents' religion. The chart indicates that 180 (60.0%) of the respondents were Christian, 111 (37.0%) were Muslim, while 9 (3.0%) practice Africa Traditional religion.

Table 5.3: Distribution of respondents by marital status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Married	103	34.3
Single	124	41.3
Separated/Divorced	44	14.7
Widow/widower	6	2.0
No Response	23	7.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.3 above shows the distribution of respondent by marital status. The data in the table shows that 103 (34.3%) of the respondents were married, 124 (41.3%) were single, 44 (14.7%) of the respondents were either separated or divorced, while 6 (2.0%) of the respondents were widows/widowers.

Table 5.4: Distribution of respondents by level of education

Level of education	Frequency	Percent
None	20	6.7
Primary Education	53	17.7
SSCE	87	29.0
OND/HND/B.Sc.	96	32.0
Post Graduate	44	14.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.4 shows distribution of respondents by level of education. The table indicates that 20 (6.7%) of them had no formal education, 53 (17.7%) had primary education, 87 (29.0%) had Senior Secondary School Certificate, 96 (32.0%) were educated up to tertiary level, while 44 (14.7%) had post graduate education. This figure shows that majority of respondents hold either OND/HND/B.Sc. degree.

Table 5.5: Distribution of respondents by employment status

Employment status	Frequency	Percent
Employed	70	23.3
Unemployed	138	46.0
Self-employed	65	21.7
No Response	27	9.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.5 shows distribution of respondents by employment status. The table indicates that 70 (23.3%) of the respondents were employed, 138 (46.6%) of the respondents were unemployed, while 65 (21.7%) were self-employed. This implies that majority of the respondents were unemployed. This data affirms the fact that majority of Nigerian youths are unemployed.

Table 5.6: Distribution of respondents by level of income

Level of income	Frequency	Percent
Below 5,000	52	17.3
5,000-25,000	105	35.0
26,000-45,000	59	19.7
46,000-65,000	47	15.7
66,000-85,000	13	4.3
86,000-105,000	4	1.3
106,000 & Above	8	2.7
No response	12	4.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.6 shows distribution of respondents by level of income. The data contained in the table indicates that 52 (17.3%) of the respondents earn below 5,000 naira per month, 105 (35.0%) earn between 5,000 to 25,000 naira, 59 (19.7%) earn between 26,000 to 45,000, 47 (15.7%) of the respondents earn between 46,000 to 65,000, 13 (4.3%) of the respondents earn monthly income of 66,000 to 85,000, 4 (1.3%) of the respondents earn between 86,000 to 105,000, while 12 (4.0%)

of the respondents earn 106,000 naira and above per month. This data shows that majority of the respondent in this study earn a monthly income of 5,000-25,000 which is low.

Table 5.7: Distribution of respondents by family types

Family Type	Frequency	Percent
Monogamy	175	58.3
Polygamy	45	15.0
Single Parents Family	55	18.3
No Response	25	8.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data captured in table 5.7 above shows distribution of respondents by family types. The table reveals that 175 (58.3%) of the respondents came from monogamous families, 45 (15.0%) of the respondents came from polygamous families, while 55 (18.3%) of the respondents came from single parent families.

Table 5.8: Distribution of respondents based on classification of neighbourhood/settlement environment

Neighbourhood type	Frequency	Percent
Upper class	87	29.0
Middle class	92	30.7
Lower class	121	40.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.8 above shows distribution of the respondents based on classification of neighbourhood. The table shows that 87 (29.0%) of the respondents were from “upper class” neighbourhood, 92 (30.7%) of the respondents were from “middle class” neighbourhood, while 121 (40.3%) of the respondents were from “lower class” neighbourhood.

5.3 PLACE OF RESIDENCE AND URBAN CRIME

Table 5.9: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever experienced street fighting in their area

Street fighting	Frequency	Percent
No	163	54.3
Yes	137	45.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.9 above shows distribution of the respondents based on whether they had ever experienced street fighting in their area. The table indicates that more than half of the respondents, 163 (54.3%), had never experienced street fighting, while 137 (45.7%) of the respondents had experienced street fighting.

Chart 1.2: Distribution of Respondents by their views on the frequency of crime in their neighbourhood

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Chart 5.2 above shows distribution of the respondents based on how often they experience street fighting in their neighbourhood, the chart shows that 49 (16.3%) of the respondents experience street fighting “very often” in their areas of residence, 53 (17.6%) of the respondents experience

street fighting “often” in their areas of residence, 28 (9.3%) of the respondents rarely experience street fighting in their areas of residence, while 162 (54.0%) of the respondents never experienced street fighting in their places of residence.

Table 5.10: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been prevented from going to work, school or any other daily routine activity as a result of street fighting

Prevented from observing a routine activity	Frequency	Percent
No	174	58.0
Yes	126	42.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.10 above shows distribution of the respondents based on whether they have ever been prevented from going to work, school or any other daily routine activity as a result of street fighting. The table reveals that 174 (58.0%) of the respondents have never been prevented from their routine activities compared to 126 (42.0%) of the respondents that have been prevented from going to work before.

Table 5.11: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been involved in street fighting

Ever involved in street fighting	Frequency	Percent
No	242	80.7
Yes	55	18.3
No Response	3	1.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.11 shows distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been involved in street fighting. The table shows that 55 (18.3%) of the respondents have been involved in the act street fighting.

Table 5.12: Distribution of respondents based on whether there are any noticeable rival gangs that perpetrate street fighting in their area

Noticeable rival gang	Frequency	Percent
No	152	50.7
Yes	126	42.0
No Response	22	7.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.12 shows distribution of respondents based on whether there are any noticeable rival gangs that perpetrate street fighting in their area. The table reveals that 126 (42.0%) of the respondents have notice the present of rival gangs that perpetrated violence in their area of residence compared to 152 (50.7%) that have never noted the presence of such rival gangs in their area.

Table 5.13: Distribution of respondents based on whether they were a member of any rival gang that perpetrate street fighting in their area

Violent gang membership	Frequency	Percent
No	244	81.3
Yes	41	13.7
No Response	15	5.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.13 shows distribution of respondents based on whether they are members of any rival gangs that perpetrate street fighting in their areas. The table indicates that majority of the respondents, 244 (81.3%), do not belong to any rival gang that perpetrate street fighting. However, 41 (13.7%) of the respondents belong to rival gang that perpetrate street fighting.

While majority of the respondents do not belong to any rival gang, data obtained from qualitative study suggest that majority of those that perpetrate street fighting were affiliated to gang. As one of the respondents for the interview said:

“Many of the large scale street fights that occur here [Mushin] are as a result of rivalry between two opposing gangs. They may be tagged with a particular name and they may also operate without a name. If they feel like one of their members has been cheated, they may decide to stage a fight on the street with the opposing gang and any unfortunate passerby may be a victim” (46 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

Similar view is also shared by another respondent who explained that:

“Some of them may not belong to a gang per se but they may feel affiliated with certain people because they live on the same street or came from the same place. So, when they hear there is a fight between the group they feel affiliated with and another group, they will join them in the fight and before you know it, it turns to a large street fight” (39 years old, male, Eti-osa LGA).

Another respondent stated that

“Street fighting is not a fight between two people; it is a fight among a group of people. So when there is street fighting, the first thing is to ask who are those involved and what are they fighting about. Young people that are involved in fighting on the street are definite gang or association members. They may not necessarily be a criminal group, but they have a bond that connects them”.

The respondents also explained the importance of identifying rival gangs to security and prevention of violence. In his words:

“As police officers, we must always know groups that are prone to violence and prevent them from carrying out violence rather than waiting for it to happen before we deploy our men” (42 years old, male, Mushin LGA)

Table 5.14: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been injured as a result of street fighting in their area

Injured as a result of street fighting before	Frequency	Percent
No	218	72.7
Yes	52	17.3
No Response	30	10.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.14 shows that vast majority of the respondent have never been injured as a result of street fighting. More precisely, the table shows that 218 (72.7%) of the respondents have been involved never sustained injury as a result of street fighting, while 52 (17.3%) of the respondents have sustained at least an injury as a result of street fighting before.

Table 5.15: Distribution of respondents based on whether any death occurred due to street fighting in their area

Death occurrence as a result of street fighting	Frequency	Percent
No	270	90.0
Yes	17	5.7
No Response	13	4.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.15 above distribution of respondents based on whether they know any death occurrence due to street fighting in their area. The table shows that 17 respondents had witnessed or know of at least a death occurrence in their area resulting from the act of street fighting.

Table 5.16: Respondents’ views on attributes that can be associated with youths that perpetrate street fighting in their area

Attributes of youths that perpetrate street fighting	Frequency	Percent
Unemployment	143	47.7
Lack of parental control	52	17.3
Homelessness	40	13.3
Drug/alcohol abuse	38	12.7
No Response	27	9.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

The table above shows distribution of the respondents based on their views on attributes that can be associated with youths that perpetrate street fighting in their area. The table shows that majority of respondents, 143 (47.7%) attribute unemployment with youths that perpetrate street fighting in their area, 52 (17.3%) of the respondents attribute lack of parental control with youths that perpetrate street fighting in their area, 40 (13.3%) attribute homelessness with youths that perpetrate street fighting in their area, while 38 (12.7%) of the respondents attribute drugs/alcohol use with youths that perpetrate street fighting in their area.

Data from qualitative study also shows that unemployment is a common attribute among youths that perpetrate domestic violence. This is vividly captured in the response of this police officer who stated that:

“Most of these youths that you see on the street in the morning and afternoon roaming around are the ones causing commotion and street fighting. Like we use to say an idle mind is devil workshop. When a young man wakes up in the morning and he’s roaming around aimlessly, anything can happen. He may see someone that will tell him to come and join a gang” (46 years, old, male, Mushin LGA).

Another police officer explained that:

“Of course many of these boys that are referred to as area boys are unemployed and some of them don’t even want to work. You will see them early in the gather in the morning arguing over unreasonable issues that do not concern them and before you know it they are fighting. The truth is that any young man that goes to work in the morning and come back at night or evening will not have reason or even strength to fight”.

This respondent explained further that lack of parental control and alcohol/drug use are some of the social factors that can be attributed to youths that perpetrate street fighting regardless of which neighbourhood the violence takes place. This view is noted in his words when he said:

“It is very common to see them hiding around and smoking or drinking alcohol when their mates are at work. So, after smoking and drinking alcohol excessively, their perception of reality is distorted and you see them misbehaving” (47 years, male, Eti-osa LGA).

Similar view is shared by this respondent who stated that:

“Unemployment is a big problem among our youths and many of them are not willing to humble themselves and take their time to learn. If a young man does not go to school and does not have any handwork, definitely he will lack and be frustrated and fighting maybe one of the way he may choose to express his anger at others”.

This respondent also explained that lack of self-esteem may cause young people to engage in street fighting. This is evident in his words when he said:

“Some of them feel like they have nothing to lose and so they can behave anyhow without any fear. You will see them bringing out bottles or class at any slightest provocation because they are not

afraid they may have injury. They don't care about themselves and others". (42 years old, male, Eti-osa LGA).

5.4 INVOLVEMENT OF RESPONDENTS IN VANDALIZATION OF PUBLIC UTILITIES

Table 5.17: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been involved in vandalization of any government utility installations

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Electric cable		
No	260	86.7
Yes	38	12.7
No Response	2	0.7
Total	300	100.0
Telephone Cable		
No	241	80.3
Yes	46	15.3
No Response	13	4.3
Total	300	100.0
Water pipeline		
No	244	81.3
Yes	41	13.7
No Response	15	5.0
Total	300	100.0
Crude oil		
No		92.0
Yes	276	4.0
No Response		4.0
	12	
	12	
Total	300	100.0

Street light		
No	225	75.0
Yes	52	17.3
No Response	23	7.7
Total	300	100.0
Others		
Bridge iron	1	0.3
Public school chairs	3	1.0
No Response	296	98.7
Total	300	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in the table 5.17 above shows distribution of the respondents based on whether they have ever been involved in vandalization of any government utility installations. Data presented in the table shows that street light is the most vandalized utility installation vandalized by 52 (17.7%) of the respondents, followed by telephone cable and water pipeline vandalized by 46 (15.3%) and 41 (13.7%) respectively.

Table 5.18: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have friends that vandalize

Have friends that vandalize	Frequency	Percent
No	246	82.0
Yes	29	9.7
No Response	25	8.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.18 above shows distribution of respondents based on whether they have friends that vandalize government utility installations. The table shows that 29 (9.7%) of the respondents have friends that are involved in act of vandilization.

Table 5.19: Distribution of respondents based on how many of their friends have ever been involved in vandalization of government utility installations

Number of friends involved in vandalization	Frequency	Percent
1-3	17	5.3
4-6	1	.3
No Response	273	94.6
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.19 above shows distribution of the respondents based on how many of their friends have ever been involved in vandalization of government utility installations. The table shows that 17 (5.3%) of the respondents have between 1-3 friends that are involved in act of vandalization, while a respondent have between 4-6 friend who are involved in act of vandalization.

Table 5.20: Distribution of respondents by whether they have friends that encourage them to join them in vandalization

Have friends that encourage vandalization	Frequency	Percent
No	277	92.3
Yes	8	2.7
No Response	15	5.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.20 shows distribution of respondents by whether they have friends that encourage them to join them in vandalization. The table shows that 8 (2.7%) of the respondents have friend that encourage them to join them in act of vandalization.

Table 5.21: Distribution of respondents based on whether their friends ever refused to share money or any materials with them because they do not join them in vandalizing government utilities

Friend refused to share	Frequency	Percent
No	279	93.0
Yes	16	5.3
No Response	5	1.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.21 shows distribution of respondents based on whether their friends ever refused to share money or any materials with them because they do not join them in vandalizing government utilities. The table shows that 16 (5.3%) of the respondents have friends that have refused to share money or any materials with them because they do not join them in vandalizing government utilities.

Table 5.22: Distribution of respondents by whether they have ever been ignored or disrespected by friends because they do not join them in vandalizing government utilities

Ignored or disrespected by friend	Frequency	Percent
No	287	95.7
Yes	8	2.7
No Response	5	1.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.22 reveals distribution of respondents by whether they have ever been ignored or disrespected by friends because they do not join them in the act of vandalizing government utilities. The table shows that 8 (2.7%) of the respondents have had friends ignored them because they do not join in the act of vandalization

Table 5.23: Distribution of respondents based on whether the first time they were involved in vandalization they did do in the mist of their friends

Vandalized with fiend the first time	Frequency	Percent
No	249	83.0
Yes	36	12.0
No Response	15	5.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.23 shows distribution of respondents based on whether the first time they were involved in vandalization they did do in the mist of their friends. The table indicates that 36 (12.0%) of the respondents that have ever been involved in vandalization did so the first time in the mist of their friends.

Table 5.24: Distribution of respondents based on whether the last time they were involved in vandalization they did do in the mist of their friends

Vandalized with fiend the last time	Frequency	Percent
No	249	83.0
Yes	38	12.7
No Response	13	4.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data captured in table 5.24 shows distribution of respondents based on whether the last time they were involved in vandalization they did do in the mist of their friends. The table shows that 38 (12.7%) of the respondents that have ever been involved in vandalization did so the last time in the mist of the friends.

Table 5.25: Composite distribution of the respondents based on whether they have ever been pressured by friends to join in vandalization of government installation utilities

Peer pressure	Frequency	Percent
Never pressured by peers	185	51.2
Ever pressured by peers	115	31.9
No Response	61	16.9
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data provided in table 5.25 above shows composite distribution of the respondents based on whether they have ever been pressured by friends to join in vandalization of government installation utilities. Having specified various (composite) variables aimed at capturing the peer pressure and involvement in vandalization, these variables are compiled (merged) using the “compute variable” function in the SPSS.

An examination of data obtained from qualitative study also shows that peer influence can play significant role in young people’s involvement in act of vandalization. This notion is vividly captured in this response:

“Many young people that indulge in criminal activities like the one you just mentioned now [vandalization] must have someone that is pushing them to join them in the act. That is why it is important for parents to monitor who their children associate with (47 years old, male, Eti-osa LGA).

Similar view is shared by another respondent who said:

Nobody exists in isolation. Young people in particular love to associate themselves with other young people in school, church, mosque or any other place they may go and from their they can easy be influenced to participate in criminal act. If they associate themselves with criminals that vandalize, the chance that they will also vandalize in the nearest future increases. Some of them may see their friends using expensive cars and gadgets and they ask them to

show them the way. If such friends tell them vandalization is the way, they can easily be convinced to join (39 years old, Male, Eti-osa LGA).

Another respondent said:

Birds of the same feather flock together. So, the influence is actually very high. If you see people that are into legal business, you see that their clique of friends is actually people in the legal business too. So when you see young people that vandalize government or private properties, if you check their clique of friends, they all have the same mentality, they all have the same standard of and style of living (46 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

However, the relationship between peer influence and involvement in vandalization or any other forms of urban crime is often complex as there may be other intervening variables that may come in between. In other words, the relationship between peer influence and vandalization is not necessarily a direct relationship. This notion was vividly captured in this response:

Hmmm, partially because though they said, show me your friend, I will show you, tell you who you are. So that is just that. They can be influenced but I have seen a young person that follows friends that are criminals but this he doesn't steal, instead he gives them gap. Whatever they give him, he doesn't join them, but they are friends. So you see that this life is what you choose and what your heart desires. So the Bible says that it is what you desire to have, that you will chase. So if you're desired to do evil, you will do evil. So, while it is true that friends can influence but what is in your own, what you determine to do within you can be another thing, the environment you are can also teach you what you don't wish to do. So all these are what can trigger people to do what they want to do (42 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

5.5 FAMILY BACKGROUND AND URBAN CRIME

Chart 1.3: Distribution of respondents by whether they have ever been involved in stealing

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Chart 1.3 above shows distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been involved in stealing. The chart shows that 69 (23.0%) of the respondents have been involved in stealing.

Table 5.26: Distribution of respondents by how often they steal

Regularity of stealing	Frequency	Percent
Very Often	6	2.0
Often	8	2.7
Rarely	45	15.0
No Response	241	80.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.26 shows distribution of respondents by how frequent they steal. The table indicates that 6 (2.0%) of the respondents steal “very often”, 8 (2.7%) of the respondents steal “often”, while 6 respondents “rarely” steal. This implies that majority of the respondents that steal rarely does so.

Table 5.27: Distribution of respondents by mother's religion

Mothers' religion	Frequency	Percent
Christianity	180	60.0
Islam	111	37.0
Traditional	9	3.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.27 above shows distribution of respondents based on their maternal parents religion. The table shows that 180 (60.0%) of the respondents maternal parent practice Christianity, 111 (37.0%) of the respondents practice Islam, while 9 (3.0%) of the respondents practice various traditional religion.

Table 5.28: Distribution of respondents by Father's religion

Fathers' religion	Frequency	Percent
Christianity	173	57.7
Islam	114	38.0
Traditional	13	4.4
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.28 above shows distribution of respondents based on their paternal parent religion. The table shows that 173 (57.70%) of the respondents paternal parent practice Christianity, 114 (38.0%) of the respondents practice Islam, while 13 (4.4%) of the respondents practice various traditional religion.

Table 5.29: Distribution of respondents by mother's level of education

Mother's level of education	Frequency	Percent
None	41	13.7
Primary Education	70	23.3
SSCE	110	36.7

OND/HND/B.Sc.	50	16.7
Post Graduate	18	6.0
No Response	11	3.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.29 above captures respondents' maternal parent level of education. The table indicates that 41 (13.7%) of respondents' maternal parent do not have any former education, 70 (23.3%) have primary education, 110 (36.7%) have Senior Secondary School Certificate, 50 (16.7%) are educated up to tertiary level, while 18 (6.0%) have post graduate education. This figure shows that majority of respondents' maternal parents SSCE certificate holders.

Table 5.30: Distribution of respondents by father's level of education

Father's level of education	Frequency	Percent
None	32	10.7
Primary Education	61	20.3
SSCE	87	29.0
OND/HND/B.Sc.	76	25.4
Post Graduate	28	9.3
No Response	16	5.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.30 above captures respondents' paternal parent level of education. The table indicates that 32 (10.7%) of respondents' paternal parent do not have any former education, 61 (20.3%) have primary education, 87 (29.0%) have Senior Secondary School Certificate, 76 (25.4%) are educated up to tertiary level, while 28 (9.3%) have post graduate education.

Table 5.31: Distribution of respondents by mother's employment status

Father's employment status	Frequency	Percent
Employed	79	26.3
Unemployed	103	34.3

Self-employed	91	30.3
No Response	27	9.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.31 shows distribution of respondents by respondents' maternal parent employment status. The table indicates that 79 (26.3%) of the respondents' maternal parent are employed, 103 (34.3%) of the respondents' maternal parent are unemployed, while 91 (30.3%) of the respondents' maternal parent are self-employed.

Table 5.32: Distribution of respondents by father's employment status

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Employed	87	29.0
Unemployed	90	30.0
Self-employed	102	34.0
No Response	21	7.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.32 shows distribution of respondents by respondents' paternal parent employment status. The table indicates that 87 (29.0%) of the respondents' paternal parent are employed, 90 (30.0%) of the respondents' paternal parent are unemployed, 102 (7.0%) of the respondents' paternal parent are self-employed.

Table 5.33: Distribution of respondents based on whether they live with their parents

Live with parents	Frequency	Percent
No	195	65.0
Yes	71	23.7
No Response	34	11.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.33 above shows distribution of respondents based on whether they live with their parents. The table reveals that majority of the respondents' 195 (65.0%) do not live with their parents compared to 71 (23.7%) of the respondents live with their parents.

Table 5.34: Distribution of respondents by family structure

Family structure	Frequency	Percent
Single parent family	59	19.7
Intact family	57	19.0
Polygamous family	57	19.0
Monogamous family	95	31.7
Others	19	6.3
No Response	13	4.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data on the respondents' family structure is captured in table 5.34 above. The table shows that 59 (19.7%) of the respondents come from a single parents family, 57 (19.0) comes from intact family, another 57 (19.0) come from polygamous family, 95 (31.7%) are from monogamous family, while 19 (6.3%) come from various other forms of family arrangement.

Table 5.35: Distribution of respondents by parents' marital status

Parents' marital status	Frequency	Percent
Married	209	69.7
Divorced/separated	52	17.3
Widow/widower	26	8.7
No Response	13	4.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data on respondents' marital status is presented in table 5.35 above. The table indicates that 209 (69.7%) of the respondents parents are married, 52 (17.3%) are either separated or divorced, 26 (8.7%) are widow/widow.

Table 5.36: Distribution of respondents by how supportive their family is

Family support	Frequency	Percent
Very supportive	160	53.3
Somewhat supportive	89	29.7
Not Supportive	34	11.3
No Response	17	5.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.36 shows distribution of respondents by how supportive their family is. 160 (53.3%) of the respondents indicate that their family is “very supportive”, 89 (29.7%) of the respondents indicate that their family is “somewhat supportive”, while 34 (11.3%) of the respondents indicate that their family is “not supportive”.

Data obtained from qualitative study shed more light on the relationship between family background and stealing among youths. Responses obtained suggest that while family background can play a role in youths’ indulgent in stealing, some youths’ indulge in stealing as a result of greed and peer influence. This is evident when a respondent explained that:

“Family inability to support that young ones, especially parents inability to provide the basic needs for their young ones can prompt them to indulge in stealing. When I said support I am not only talking about money and material things, I am also talking about moral support. When parents are able to provide for the welfare of the young ones they may have no reason to steal. But we have also seen some young guys and girls that steal despite the fact that their parents support them. So, It is a two ways thing” (42 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

Another respondent explained that:

“It is true that poor family background can cause young people to steal in order to support them self, but that will be an excuse. It is what an individual considers as an option that they will do when problem arise. We have many young people who are sponsoring themselves to school and feed themselves through personal effort without stealing anything from anybody” (47 years old, male, Eti-osa LGA).

5.6 EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT AND URBAN CRIME

Table 5.37: Distribution of respondents by whether respondents have ever used any illicit drug

Illicit drug use	Frequency	Percent
No	154	51.3
Yes	146	48.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.37 shows distribution of respondents based on whether respondents have ever used any illicit drug. The table indicates that nearly half of the respondents have used an illicit drug at a particular point in time. More precisely, the table shows that 146 (48.7%) of the respondents have used an illicit drug compared to 154 (51.3%) that have never done so.

Table 5.38: Distribution of respondents based on whether they are presently schooling

Presently schooling	Frequency	Percent
No	144	48.0
Yes	149	49.7
No Response	7	2.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

The table above shows distribution of the respondents based on whether they are presently schooling or not. The table shows 149 (49.7%) of the respondents are presently schooling compared to 149 (48.0%) that are not

The qualitative data provides more insight on the relationship between educational attainment and illicit drug use among youths. An examination of the data suggests that regardless of educational attainment, young people can use illicit drug. The data suggest that place of residence and peer pressure rather than educational attainment are more potent factors that can determine whether a young person to use illicit drug. This is evident is the notion expressed by a respondent who said:

“I don’t think education has much to do with use of illicit drug whether among youths or any other group of people. Educated people as much as uneducated people drug use illicit drugs. I think most people that use illicit drug because they have access to it in the area where they stay. In some areas you will see that drug peddling is a common thing... In such environment young people are likely to be exposed to drug use, either illicit or not” (42 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

Another respondent stated that:

“It is possible that educated people may know more about consequences of drug use and take some health precaution, but still use illicit drug. So, as far as I am concerned whether a young person is a graduate or an illiterate, he or she may still use illicit drug. What really matter is the kind of friend a young person keeps”. (46 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

Table 5.39: Distribution of respondents based on whether they drop out of school at point in their education

Presently schooling	Frequency	Percent
No	206	68.7
Yes	78	26.0
No Response	16	5.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.39 above shows distribution of the respondents based on whether they drop out of school at point in their education. The table indicates that 78 (26.0%) of the respondents dropped out of school.

Table 5.40: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have any professional qualification

Have professional qualification	Frequency	Percent
No	208	69.3
Yes	83	27.7
No Response	9	3.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.39 shows distribution of respondents based on whether they have any professional qualification. The table indicates that 83 (27.7%) of the respondents have professional qualification.

5.7 EMPLOYMENT STATUS AND URBAN CRIME

Table 5.41: Distribution of respondents by whether they have ever participated in any violent act

Participation in violent act	Frequency	Percent
No	194	64.7
Yes	103	34.3
No Response	3	1.0
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.41 shows distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever participated in any violent act. The table show that 103 (34.35) of the respondents have ever participated in violent act.

Table 5.42: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been sponsored to carry out political violence

Belongingness to any violent syndicate	Frequency	Percent
No	249	83.0
Yes	40	13.3
No Response	11	3.7
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.41 above shows distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been sponsored to carry out political violence. The table indicates that 40 (13.3%) have ever been sponsored to carry out political violence.

Table 5.43: Distribution of respondents based on whether they have ever been arrested by police for a violent act

Arrested by police	Frequency	Percent
No	224	74.7
Yes	63	21.0
No Response	13	4.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 5.43 shows distribution of the respondents based on whether they have ever been arrested by police for a violent act. The table shows that 63 (21.0%) of the respondents have ever been arrested by police for a violent act.

This quantitative data is backed with qualitative data. The qualitative study suggests that unemployment among youths is the root cause of thuggery. This is well captured in this response:

“Unemployment causes so many problems among youth of which one of them is thuggery. Many of these so called thug or area boys in this

area are unemployed. Some of them don't have work to do and some don't even want to work. They have embrace thuggery as a way of life instead of finding a job to do. Last week we arrested two boys at Ojuwoye who were causing problem for some law abiding citizen and when I looked at one of them I saw thug for life with this popular late American rapper. That is what I mean when I said they have embraced thuggery as their own way of life, but to the best of my knowledge they will change if they can find meaning job to be doing. In fact I have seen many of them changing already. To the best of my knowledge we law enforcement agent are doing our best, but these boys and girls must be engaged in a meaningful activity” (42 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

Similar opinion is also shared by this respondent who explained that:

“The number one solution to the problem of thuggery is to create job and trained all these young people that are jobless because that is also the cause of the problem in the first place”. (46 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

5.8 TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

The hypotheses formulated in this study were tested using Chi square (χ^2) statistical method. Some of the variables that were cross tabbed were merged to a *composite variable* before chi-square test was carried out. This enables the researcher to fuse several dependent variables together. The Chi-square (χ^2) formula is given as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(o-e)^2}{e}$$

Where, χ^2 \Rightarrow Chi-square

o = Observed frequency

e = Expected frequency

Σ = Summation

Degree of Freedom

The degree of freedom is the number of respondents ('r') observed in the sample size multiplied by the population ('c') parameters estimated from sample observations.

Thus d.o.f. = (r-1) (c-1)

Where r = Row

c = Column

The level of significance is 0.05 (alpha level, α)

Decision Region

The decision region is based on the rules that if the p-value (i.e. asymptomatic value) is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship. But if the p-value is higher than 0.05, then there is no relationship.

Hypothesis One:

H₁: There is a relationship between place of residence and urban crime among youths

H₀: There is no relationship between place of residence and urban crime among youths

Table 5.44: Relationship between place of residence and urban crime among youths

Experience of street fighting in area of residence	Which of these describe your settlement/neighbourhood?			Total
	Upper class	Middle class	Lower class	
Never experienced street fighting	83 (36.6%)	74 (32.6)	70 (30.8%)	227(100%)
Ever experienced street fighting	4(5.5%)	18 (27.4%)	51(69.9%)	73(100%)
Total	87(29.9%)	92 (30.7%)	121(40.3%)	300 (100%)
X²=40.398; df=2; p-value=.000				

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.44 shows that the calculated value ($\chi^2 = 40.398$, 'p' value = .000) is less than the level of significance of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. This implies that there is a relationship between place of residence and street fighting among youths vis-à-vis urban crime. Data presented in the table shows that only 4 (5.5%) of the respondents from upper class area have experienced street fighting in their area of residence, 92 (30.7%) of the respondents from middle class area have experienced street fighting in their area of residence, while 121 (40.3%) of the respondents from lower class area have experienced street fighting in their area of residence. Hence, the poorer an environment is the higher the rate of urban crime.

This finding is also corroborated by the qualitative study. The qualitative data suggests that urban crime such as street fighting is more concentrated in low income areas where there are many unemployed youths. However, urban crimes also occur in high income area but the type of urban

crimes that occur is difference from that of low income area. This view is evident when a respondent explained that:

“Every area has its own unique challenges and these challenges often affect the way people think and react to situations. As far as I am concerned street fighting cannot happen anywhere, it can only occur in poor areas where their youths are mostly unemployed and poor because when young people are unemployed and indulge in habit such as smoking and drinking, they can do and undo. I will tell you for instance as a police officer I work here [Eti-Osa LGA], but my house is at Ketu. I have seen many incidence of street fighting in Ketu but I have not witnessed it here. But that does not mean that young people don’t commit crime here too, but not street fighting. What does that tells you? It shows that street fighting among young people is not a problem everywhere. Young people that fight on the street are area boys that are unemployed” (47 years old, male, Eti-osa LGA).

Similar opinion was also shared by a respondent who suggested that differences in level of education and skills are responsible for variation in type of urban crime committed among youths.

“Street fighting does not occur in certain areas as much it occurs in other areas in this Lagos. This depends on the caliber of youths that are present there. Here in Mushin where I am serving currently as a police officer, many incidence of street fighting have occurred but I can boast that the incidence of street fighting has reduced significantly over the years. In this area, many youths are unemployed and not learned. So, that is why you see them fighting with cutlass and life on the street. In big men areas you may not see the incidence of street fighting but they also commit sophisticated crime than even youth here... credit card and internet fraud is common over there [high income area] because those youths are educated and they have the skill to commit such crimes” (42 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

Hypothesis Two:

H₁: There is a relationship between peer pressure and urban crime among youths

H₀: There is no relationship between peer pressure and urban crime and youths

Table 5.45: Relationship between peer pressure and urban crime among youths

Have you ever been involved in vandalism of any government utility installations?	Do you have friends that encourage you to join them in vandalizing government utilities?		Total
	No	Yes	
Never involved in vandalism	138 (58.0%)	100 (42.0%)	238 (100%)
Ever involved in vandalism	35 (79.5%)	9 (20.5%)	44 (100%)
Total	173 (61.3%)	109(38.7%)	282 (100%)
	X²=10.310; df=2; p-value=.006		

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.45 shows that the calculated value ($\chi^2 = 10.310$, 'p' value = .006) is less than the level of significance of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis (H^0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H^1) is accepted. This implies that there is a relationship between peer pressure and vandalism of government utilities vis-à-vis urban crime among youths. The result of this quantitative data is also supported by qualitative data obtained.

“Young people influence one another both positively and negatively. It depends on the type of friends a young person surrounds him or herself with. That is why they say ‘show me your friend and I will show you who you are’. Many young men that commit vandalism do so with friend at first before they can be on their own. Vandalization or any crime is like learning a trade at first. If you have never vandalized before, you will need someone to give you courage that you can do it and you will also have to learn from the person” (39 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

A similar view is also shared by a respondent who explained that desire to live a flashy live that friends are living can compel a young person to commit urban crime. In his word:

“Peer group is very influential and most of the people involved in vandalization are young people that are desperate. These are the people that have seen that their friends have made it. They have seen people, their friends with flashy car. They too want to feel among, you know, they want to make it, they want to feel happy, they want to feel high ray, they want to join, they also want to go to clubs and spend money, they want to ride on big cars and live a flamboyant lifestyle. So in the process, peer groups might actually influence them by convincing them to join it. One common characteristic of young people is that they want to do what their friends are doing in order to feel belong. They want to use the latest iphone and feel belong after run they are not in village. This desire can compel them to commit crime” (42 years old, respondents, Mushin LGA).

Hypothesis Three:

H₁: There is a relationship between family background and urban crime among youths.

H₀: There is no relationship between family background and urban crime and youths.

Table 5.46: Relationship between family background and urban crime among youths

Which of these describes your family background?	Have you ever been involved in stealing?		Total
	No	Yes	
Monogamy	121 (70.8%)	50 (29.2%)	171 (100%)
Polygamy	36 (83.7%)	7 (16.3%)	43 (100%)
Single parent family	36(66.7)	18(33.3%)	54(100%)
Total	193 (72.0%)	75(28.0%)	268 (100%)
X²=3.824; df=2; p-value=.148			

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.46 shows that the calculated value ($\chi^2 = 3.824$, 'p' value= .148) is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is rejected. This implies that there is no relationship between family background and urban crime among youths.

This finding is also similar to what was obtained from qualitative data. Responses from key informant suggests that while family, particularly parents' inability to provide for their young ones can prompt them to still, peer influence and greediness is a more potent explanation of stealing among young people. This is noted in this response of this law enforcement agent:

“Every human being has instinct for survival. So when parents are unable to support their children who are young, these children may be tempted to steal. But that is not sufficient reason to steal. Many of us grew up with little or no family support and we worked hard rather than stealing from anyone in order to be somebody. The reason why many young people steal is because they are influence by bad friends. Like we use to say that ‘evil company corrupt good manner: When a young person works and associate with good friends, even without family support, he will navigate through

many difficulties without stealing. Personally, I went and finish my university education without any family so if I can do it, young people of nowadays can do it as well” (47 years old, male, Eti-Osa).

Similar view was also shared by this respondent who said:

“Family support is very important to young people in many ways, especially financial support to do basic things. But let’s face the fact here many young people are surviving with minimal family support. The problem with young people that are stealing is greediness. They want to do what they are not up to. Last week, we arrested a young lady that stole iphone 7 from a woman. What does she wants to do with it? Because she has stolen the phone for over a week before she was arrested and she didn’t sell it, and she also has a good android phone of her own that her parents bought for her. Tell me is that as a result of lack of family support. She wants to use what her parents cannot afford to give her. That is pure greediness...” (46 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

Hypothesis Four:

H₁: There is a relationship between educational attainment and urban crime among youths.

H₀: There is no relationship between educational attainment and urban crime and youths.

Table 5.47: Relationship between educational attainment and urban crime among youths

Illicit drug use	Educational attainment					Total
	None	Primary	SSCE	OND/HN D/B.Sc	Post-Graduate	
Never use illicit drug	14 (9.1%)	26(16.9%)	45 (29.2%)	45 (29.2%)	24(15.6%)	154(100%)
Ever use illicit drug	6(4.1%)	27 (18.5%)	42(28.8%)	51(34.9%)	20(13.7%)	146(100%)
Total	20(6.7%)	53(17.7%)	(87(27.0%)	96(32.0%)	44(14.7%)	300 (100%)
X²=3.850; df=4; p-value=.427						

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.46 shows that the calculated value ($x^2= 3.850$, ‘p’ value= .428) is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis (H^0) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H^1) is rejected. This implies that there is no relationship between educational attainment and urban crime among youths. Similarly, data obtained from qualitative data also suggest there education attainment have little to do with use of illicit drug use. The qualitative study, however; suggest that access to this drug is a major factor and that this drug is ready more available in low income areas (ghetto) than middle and upper class areas. This view is vividly captured in this response below:

“Regardless of whether a young person is educated or not, rich or poor he or she can use and abuse illicit drug. What matters to us as law enforcement agents is access to such drugs. Who are the people selling these drugs? Because it is illicit, it shouldn’t be sold to people. Unfortunately, some criminal syndicates are making fortune with sales of these illicit drugs. We are partnering with NAFDAC and other relevant agencies to address this

issue. What I think is interesting to know is that these drugs are more available in some area, ... especially the ghetto areas” (39 years old police, Mushin LGA).

Similarly another respondent opined:

*“To the best of my knowledge, people use illicit drug or even sell it regardless of their level of education... however this respondents opined that the extent to which illicit drugs are accessible or use is difficult to know because it involve secrecy. In his word: *Because illicit is not sold in the openly, it is not easy to say whether it is easily accessible in one area than other” (42 years old, male, Eti-osa).**

Hypothesis Five:

H₁: There is a relationship between employment status and urban crime among youths.

H₀: There is no relationship between employment status and urban crime and youths.

Table 5.48: Relationship between employment status and urban crime among youths

Thuggery	What is your employment status?			Total
	Employed	Unemployed	Self-employed	
Never involved in thuggery activities	63(29.2%)	97 (44.9%)	56 (25.9%)	216(100%)
Ever involved in thuggery activities	6(14.3%)	28 (66.7%)	8(19.0%)	42(100%)
Total	69(26.7%)	125 (28.3%)	64(25.0%)	258 (100%)
X²=19.133; df=2; p-value=.004				

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Data presented in table 5.48 shows that the calculated value ($\chi^2 = 19.133$, 'p' value= .004) is less than the level of significance of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis (H^0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H^1) is accepted. This implies that there is a relationship between employment status and thuggery. This result is overwhelmingly supported by qualitative study. This is evident when a respondent said:

“Unemployment is a major problem among youth. Many young guys that are involved in thuggery activities are unemployed youths. Election is around the corner now so we are working hard to prevent police from recruiting these young lads to carry out violence in order to achieve their own selfish goal. Unemployed youths are their particular target for recruitment because they will want to do something to earn money even it involves violence and risk”. (42 years old, male Mushin LGA).

Another respondent simply said:

It is a common knowledge that thugs are unemployed (46 years old, male, Mushin LGA).

5.9 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The purpose of this section is to link this study to earlier research works in terms of explanations and interpretations which have been offered concerning the relationship between social and environmental factors and urban crime among youths. Hence, this section is built on earlier studies mentioned in the literature review as well as theories stated in previous chapter to discuss the differences and similarities of this current study to previous research works.

Firstly, the study found a relationship between place of residence and street fighting among young people. The result of the study shows that urban crime is more concentrated in low income areas where there are more unemployed youths; however, urban crime also occur in high income areas but the type of urban crime that occur in low income areas is different from that of high income areas. Evidence from qualitative data suggests that more sophisticated crimes such as credit card and internet fraud are more common in high income areas compared to lower income area where urban crime like street violence is more rampant. This result is in tandem with social disorganization theory which indicates how structurally disadvantaged neighbourhoods, characterized by high levels of poverty, unemployment, single-parent households, racial and ethnic heterogeneity, and residential mobility are likely to have higher rates of crime (Sampson, 1997; Shaw and McKay, 1942). This finding is also supported by earlier study conducted by Agbola (1997), who noted that in Lagos street fighting, hooliganism and drug dealing were more in high density residential areas. His study demonstrated that there are notable geographical variations in the pattern of street violence and that these variations imply that street fighting is more concentrated in high density neighbourhoods. Also, Oluogunjobi (2016) clearly demonstrated the fact that street fighting is not equally distributed in Lagos State by identifying 10 areas and streets where crime, including street fighting, occurs regularly. The identified areas include: Anibaba and Itu Nla (Ikorodu); Ojelade and Oju Irin (Mushin); Igbo Olomu and Isawo (Ikorodu); Ilaje (Bariga); Odunfa and Onala (Lagos Island); Shibiri (Okokomaiko); and Obadore (Igando). A close look at this areas shows that they are basically low income neighbourhood with poor basic infrastructure. Some of these areas can also be categorized as high density areas.

Secondly, the study found that peer influence is correlated with urban crime. The result of the study suggests that young people desire to live flamboyant life exhibited by their friends can prompt them to commit crime. The result is corroborated with differential association theory which

posits that criminal behavior is learned from contact with those who maintain criminal attitudes and practices. The process of learning criminal behavior is by association with criminals. The result is also in tandem with Nsofor 2013 assertion that peer associates have a great influence on the lifestyle of their members. Nsofor stated further that group association as an agent of socialization, determines to a large extent, what social codes an individual learns. This implies that individuals whose core group members believe and act criminal within norms will learn and internalize more of criminal codes than those that conform to the norms of the society.

Thirdly, the study found no relationship between family background and urban crime among youths. The finding of the study suggests that poor family background is a necessary but not a sufficient condition for involvement in urban crime. This result contradicts Chumbe, Sarah, Martha and Helen (2013) findings that children who come from families who have the vice of stealing are likely to carry over the same behavior in later life. In their study, all principals and four out of six teacher counselors revealed that family background was one of the causes of stealing in schools. From the students 110 students who were 73% of the sampled students were of the view that family background was the cause of stealing in the sampled schools.

Fourthly, the study also found there is no relationship between educational attainment and urban crime among youths. However; this study suggests that urban crime like illicit use is determined by accessibility rather than educational attainment. The study shows that accessibility in low income areas (ghetto) is higher than middle and upper class areas. This result is similar to earlier study conducted by Bachman, O'Malley and Johnston (1980). These researchers used a composite measure of parents' educational attainment, which serves as a rough indicator of family socioeconomic status (SES). The result of the measure shows relatively little correlation with the four drug use measures. The largest association with parental education is a correlation of 0.16 with alcohol use by females, which contrasts with a correlation of only .04 for males. Since males in general average higher in alcohol use than females, this means that in families with higher parental education the drinking patterns of male and female high school seniors are not so widely different, whereas in families with less parental education the female seniors drink distinctly less than the males.

Lastly, this study found a relationship between employment status and urban crime among youths. This is in line with Adebayo (2013) assertion that unemployment and violent crime, including

thuggery and all other forms of urban crimes, are always thought to work hand in hand, with an increase in one leading to a rise in the other, and vice versa.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the summary of key findings of the study and implications of the study for policy and social work practice. Conclusion is also drawn in this chapter and recommendations are proffered in relation to the findings of the research study.

6.2 Summary

The primary goal of this study has been to examine social and environmental determinants of urban crime among youths. Increase in crime rate in major urban centre globally has been an issue of concern for governments, security agents, social researchers and urban dwellers. Another salient concern is the involvement of youths in crime instead of productive activities that is capable of bringing about sustainable social and economic development. As such, it is pertinent that the problem is given special attention. The study sought to understand the relationship between place of residence, peer pressure, family background, educational attainment, employment status and urban crime among youths. The study adopted both quantitative and qualitative research approach to find out if there is any relationship between these socio-environmental factors and youths involvement in urban.

6.3 Summary of key finding

Following empirical data collection and analysis, the prominent findings of this study are summarized below in tandem with the specific objectives of the study:

1. The study found a relationship between place of residence and urban crime among young people. The result of the study demonstrates that urban crime is not equally distributed among low and high income areas as it is more concentrated in low income areas where there are more unemployed youths. The study also shows that there is variation in type of urban crime that is committed in low and high income areas; whereas crime like street fighting is more likely to occur in low income areas, sophisticated crime like credit card and internet fraud are more common in high income area.

2. The study also reveals that peer group is a significant factor in young people's involvement in crime. The findings of the study suggest that young people's desire to live flamboyant lifestyle exhibits by their friends can prompt them to get involved.

3. Findings of this study suggest that there is no relationship between family background and youth involvement in urban crime. The study suggest that rather than family background, greediness and peer group influence are the factors that make young people get involved in urban crime.

4. The study also found no relationship between educational attainment and urban crime among youths. However; this study suggests that urban crime like illicit use is determined by accessibility rather than educational attainment.

5. Finally, the study demonstrates a strong relationship between unemployment and urban crime among youths. The study suggest further that more unemployed youths are found in poor neighborhood and as such variation in urban crime rate between this two strata is as a result of differences in youth unemployment rate.

6.4 Implications for policy

The findings of this study are of great importance to policy makers who wish to improve security of life and properties and also promote youth development. With right investment, the youth population can play a more significant role in social and economic development of the state. Unfortunately, many of these youths are a major source of insecurity to the society. Therefore, there is a need to review current youth policy and mechanisms through which this policy is implemented with a special focus on education and creating employment opportunities for youths. Policy-maker must also realize that any act of crime perpetrated against any citizen is a violation of human fundamental human right, and it has consequences for national development and image; individuals' health and wellbeing; and overall quality of life. Therefore, it is work towards building improved security agencies that will bring about infiltration of criminal networks, targeting the proceeds of crime, and statutes allowing prosecution for conspiracy or a broad range of racketeering offences. The most important single factor leading to significant reductions in crime would be to increase the probability of capture and conviction given an offence. This can only be achieved when law enforcement agencies are well equipped and trained to perform their statutory role.

6.5 Conclusion and recommendation

A range of social and environmental factors such as place of residence, employment status and peer pressure plays significant role in youth involvement in all sought of urban crimes such as street fighting, vandalization, thuggery and illicit drug use/peddling among many other. Differentiation in youth involvement in criminal activities appears to be a reflection of social and economic in equality. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The State should review it current urban planning and also embrace community-based approaches, in which communities take ownership of the various initiatives; reduction of risk factors by focusing on groups (such as those popularly recognized as area boy) that are likely to be perpetrators and victims of crime; and strengthening of social capital through initiatives that seek to develop the ability of individuals and communities to respond to problems of crime and violence. The combination of several of these approaches all of which are especially suitable for implementation at the local level into a systematic programme, driven by a broad strategy and based upon a careful understanding of the local context seems more likely to succeed than the ad hoc application of individual initiatives. This recommendation is made based on the fact that this study finding that crime is higher in certain place of residence. It is assumed that people residing in a particular area know youths that are likely to be perpetrators of crime and they can take action to prevent them from carrying out criminal activities if empowered
2. The current state of youth unemployment in Nigeria, particularly in Lagos metropolis, should be addressed holistically and with sense of urgency. To address this challenge, agriculture should be made attractive to young people as it is a viable source of investment for young people. This will not only reduce cybercrime among youth but it will also bring about a swift transition from subsistence to commercialized farming, a development that will be beneficial to Nigeria economic growth.
3. Education curriculum should be reviewed at all level of education to incorporate skills acquisition exercise and entrepreneurship development in order to enhance productivity among youth.

4. There is also a need to strengthen the formal criminal justice and policing systems. It is important that the police and the criminal justice systems are 'fit for purpose' and are seen as key contributors to the fight against crime. A vital issue is the need to boost public confidence that the police and criminal justice systems will play their part in this process effectively.

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APPENDIX I
UNIVERSITY OF LAGOS
FACULTIES OF SOCIAL SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF SOCIOLOGY
AKOKA-YABA, LAGOS

Dear Respondent,

My name is WILLOUGHBY, Yetunde Hope, an undergraduate student of University of Lagos, studying Social Work at the Faculty of Social sciences. I am conducting a research study as partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc) degree in Social Work. The title of my study is *Social and Environmental Determinants of Urban Crime among Youths in Lagos State*. I hereby request for your utmost attention in filling the questionnaire and your sincerity is also needed to make this research work a successful one.

Note: You are **not** required to supply your name and address therefore, your secret is safe, any information supplied will not be made open to the public, hence, you are guaranteed of confidentiality. The questionnaire should take less than 15 minutes of your time.

I therefore, request for your consent in participating in the study

Thank You!

SECTION A: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS			
S/NO	QUESTIONS	RESPONSE	CODE
1	Sex	Male Female	1 2
2.	Age range	18-20 21-23 24-26 27-29 30-32 33-35	1 2 3 4 5 6
3.	What is your ethnic group?	Yoruba Igbo Hausa/Fulani Others	1 2 3 4

4.	What religion do you practice?	Christianity Islam Traditional Others	1 2 3 4
5.	What is your marital status?	Married Single Separated/Divorced Widow/Widower	1 2 3 4
6.	Level of education	None Primary Education SSCE OND/HND/B.SC Post graduate	1 2 3 4 5
7.	What is your employment status?	Employed Unemployed Self-employed	1 2 3
8.	What is your level of income?	Below 5,000 5,000-25,000 26,000-45,000 46,000-65,000 66,000-85,000 86,000-105,000 106,000 & above	1 2 3 4 5 6 7
9.	Which of these describes your family background?	Monogamy Polygamy Single parent family	1 2 3
10.	Which of these describe your settlement/neighborhood?	Upper class Middle class Lower class	1 2 3
11.	Which Local Government Area do you reside?	Eti-Osa LGA Mushin LGA	1 2
SECTION B: NEIGHBORHOOD FACTORS AND CRIME			
12.	Have you ever experienced any form of crime in your area?	Yes No	1 2
	If yes, which of the following forms of crime has ever taken place in your area?	Street fighting Vandalisation Burglary Stealing/theft Armed robbery Rape Kidnapping Others (specify)..... (Tick as many as are applicable)	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

13.	Which of these crimes are the commonest in your area?	Street fighting Vandalisation Burglary Stealing/theft Armed robbery Rape Kidnapping Others (specify)..... (Tick as many as are applicable)	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
14.	What time does/do this crime occur in your area?	During the day Night At all times	1 2 3
15.	Who are those that engage in crime in your area?	Mostly youths Mostly adults Mostly juveniles All of the above	1 2 3 4
16.	Have you ever been involved in any of these following activities?	Street fighting Vandalisation Burglary Stealing/theft Armed robbery Rape Kidnapping Others (specify)..... (Tick as many as are applicable)	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
17.	What were/was your reason(s) for taking part in such activities?	Poverty Friends Injustice Drug/alcohol Politics Others (Specify).....	1 2 3 4 5 6
18.	Have you ever been arrested by the police?	Yes No	1 2
19.	If yes, what offence were you arrested for?	Street fighting Vandalisation Burglary Stealing/theft Armed robbery Rape Kidnapping Others (specify)..... (Tick as many as are applicable)	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

SECTION C: PLACE OF RESIDENCE AND STREET FIGHTING			
20.	Have you ever experienced street fighting in your area?	Yes No	1 2
21.	If yes, how would you describe the occurrence of street fighting in your neighborhood in the past one year?	Very often Often Rarely Never	1 2 3 4
22.	Have you ever been prevented from going to work, school or any other daily routine activity as a result of street fighting in your area?	Yes No	1 2
23.	Have you ever been a part of street fighting?	Yes No	1 2
24.	Are there any noticeable rival gangs that perpetrate street fighting in your area?	Yes No	1 2
25.	Are you a member of any rival gangs that perpetrate street fighting in your area?	Yes No	1 2
26.	Have you have been injured as a result of street fighting in your area?	Yes No	1 2
27.	Has any death occurred due to street fighting in your area?	Yes No	1 2
28.	What was the cause of the last street fight you witnessed in your area?	Fight for supremacy Opposite sex Drug/alcohol intoxication Politics Money Others (specify)	1 2 3 4 5 6
29.	Which of these attributes can you associate with youths that perpetrate street fighting in your area?	Unemployed Uneducated Lack parental control Homelessness Drug/Alcohol abuse Others (specify) Tick as many as are applicable)	1 2 3 4 5 6
SECTION D: PEER GROUP INFLUENCE AND VANDALIZATION			
30.	Have you ever been involved in vandalization of any of these government utility installations?	Electric cable Telephone cable Water pipeline Crude oil pipeline Gas pipeline Street light Others (specify) Tick as many as are applicable)	1 2 3 4 5 6 7
31.	Do you have friends that vandalize any of these government utility installations?	Yes No	1 2

32.	If yes, how many of your friends have ever been involved in vandalization of government utility installations?	1-3 4-6 7-9 10 and above	1 2 3 4
33.	Do you have friends that encourage you to join them in vandalizing government utilities?	Yes No	1 2
34.	Have your friends refused to share money or any materials with you because you do not join them in vandalizing government utilities?	Yes No	1 2
35.	Do you have to join your friends in vandalism in order to join please them or “feel belong”?	Yes No	1 2
36.	Have you ever been ignored or disrespected by your friends because you do not join them in vandalizing government utilities?	Yes No	1 2
37.	If you have ever been involved in vandalization of government utilities, did you do so the first time in the mist of your friend?	Yes No	1 2
38.	If you have ever been involved in vandalization of government utilities, did you do so the last time in the mist of your friend?	Yes No	1 2
SECTION E: FAMILY BACKGROUND AND STEALING			
39.	Have you ever been involved in stealing?	Yes No	1 2
40.	If yes, how often do you steal?	Very often Often Rarely	1 2 3
41.	What religion does your mother practice?	Christianity Islam Traditional Others	1 2 3 4
42.	What religion does your father practice?	Christianity Islam Traditional Others	1 2 3 4
43.	What is your mother’s level of education?	None Primary Education SSCE OND/HND/B.SC Post graduate	1 2 3 4 5
44.	What is your father’s level of education?	None Primary Education SSCE OND/HND/B.SC Post graduate	1 2 3 4 5
45.	What is your mother’s employment status?	Employed Unemployed Self-employed	1 2 3
46.	What is your father’s employment status?	Employed Unemployed Self-employed	1 2 3

47.	Do you live with your parents?	Yes No	1 2
48.	If yes, which of your parents do you stay with?	Both parents Mother Father	1 2 3
49.	What is your mother's level of education?	None Primary SSCE OND/HND B.SC Postgraduate	1 2 3 4 5 6
50.	What is your father's level of education?	None Primary SSCE OND/HND B.SC Postgraduate	1 2 3 4 5 6
51.	What is your mother's level of income?	Below 5,000 5,000-25,000 26,000-45,000 46,000-65,000 66,000-85,000 86,000-105,000 105,000 & above	1 2 3 4 5 6 7
52.	What is your father's level of income?	Below 5,000 5,000-25,000 26,000-45,000 46,000-65,000 66,000-85,000 86,000-105,000 105,000 & above	1 2 3 4 5 6 7
53.	How supportive is your family to your welfare?	Very supportive Somewhat supportive Not supportive	1 2 3
SECTION F: EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT AND ILLICIT DRUGS USE			
54.	Have you ever used any illicit drug?	Yes No	1 2
55.	If yes, which illicit drug have you used in the past one year	Tramadol Rohypnol Codeine Cocaine Heroin Others (specify)	1 2 3 4 5 6
56.	Are you presently schooling?	Yes No	1 2

57.	At what level of your education did you drop of school	Primary SSCE OND/HND B.SC	1 2 3 4
57.	If not, did you drop out of school at any point in time?	Yes No	1 2
58.	Do you have any professional qualification?	Yes No	1 2
SECTION G: EMPLOYMENT STATUS AND THUGGERY			
59.	Do you ever participate in any violent act?	Yes No	1 2
60.	Do you belong to any violent syndicate?	Yes No	1 2
61.	Have you ever been sponsored to carry out political violence?	Yes No	1 2
62.	Have you ever been arrested by law enforcement agents for a violent or criminal act?	Yes No	1 2
63.	If yes, how many times have you been arrested in the past one year?	Once Twice Thrice More than thrice	1 2 3 4

Thanks!

APPENDIX I

KEY INFORMANT INTERVIEW GUIDE

Section A: Socio-demographic data of respondents

QUESTION: Please, introduce yourself.

Probe

- Your age, religion, ethnic background, marital status and your rank as a police officer?
- How long have you been serving as a police officer in Lagos State?

Section B: Place of Residence and Street Fighting

QUESTION: Based on your experience as a police officer, do you think the occurrence of street fighting is more concentrated in certain areas than others?

Probe

- If yes, what are the peculiar social and environmental attributes of areas where street fight occurs more frequently in Lagos State?
- In your view as a serving police officer, do you think there is variation in occurrence of street fighting between high population density areas and middle/low population density areas in Lagos State?
- In your view, is there variation in occurrence of street fighting between low and middle/high income areas in Lagos State?
- How would you describe the prevalence of street fighting in this local government area of Lagos State where you are currently serving as a police officer?

Section C: Peer group influence and vandalization of government utilities

QUESTION: What do you think about peer group influence and youth involvement in vandalization of government utilities?

Probe

- Based on your experience, do you think having friends that are involved in vandalism increases the likelihood that a young person will be involved in the criminal act?
- In what ways do you think friends can influence young person to join.

Section D: Family background and stealing

QUESTION: What do you think is the influence of family background on youth involvement in the act of stealing?

Probe

- Based on cases you have handled, how do you think parental income impact on youth indulgent in stealing?
- What do you think is the impact of parental educational attainment on youth involvement in stealing?
- How do you think parental level of income impacts on youth indulgent in stealing?

Section E: Educational attainment and illicit drugs use

QUESTION: How does educational attainment impact on illicit drugs use?

Probe

- Do you think there is significant difference in illicit drugs use among youths that have high level of education and those that have low education?

Section F: Employment status and thuggery

QUESTION: What impact does youth employment status play on their involvement in thuggery activities?

Probe

- In your own view, do you think there is significant difference in susceptibility to thuggery between employed and unemployed youth?